

115966 – PREFER

**Patient Preferences in Benefit-Risk Assessments during the Drug Life
Cycle**

WP3 – Case studies

Report on additional case studies (D3.8)

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Document History

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V1	06 Dec 2021	First draft
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Abstract

The objective of Task 3.8 was to conduct prospective case studies additional to the three core case studies in PREFER. Within this task, four industry-led case studies were conducted in disease areas related to Myocardial infarction, Chronic pain, Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and Hemophilia. Additionally, four case studies were conducted led by academia in disease areas related to Diabetes, Hemophilia, Multiple Myeloma and Rheumatoid Arthritis. These additional studies cover several decision points of different stakeholders in the medical product lifecycle. Also, they cover a large number of PREFER methodological research questions from comparison of Discrete Choice Experiments with Best-Worst-Scaling and Swing weighting as well as variations across patient groups and the assessment of educational tools. This report describes the main characteristics of the 8 additional case studies and contains summaries of all studies.

Information within this report that may influence other PREFER tasks

Linked task	Points from this report that are of particular relevance to the linked task
3.9 Assessment of Case Studies based on criteria from WP2 and cross-case study assessment	Assessment of study results regarding research questions
3.10 Transferability of patient preference study results	Assessment of transferability of study results
4.3 Final recommendations	Consideration of study results regarding research questions
4.4 Operational guide on best practice for conduct of patient preference studies	Consideration of studies' experience regarding study conduct

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Background

The European public-private partnership PREFER ('Patient Preferences in Benefit and Risk Assessments during the Drug Life Cycle') was launched in 2016. PREFER is a 5-year project, funded jointly by Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 (IMI; Europe's largest public-private initiative which aims to aid the development of better and safer medicines) and the European pharmaceutical industry (represented by EFPIA, the European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations). PREFER aims to strengthen patient-centric decision-making throughout the Medical Product Lifecycle (MPLC) by developing evidence-based recommendations to advise the different stakeholders (i.e., pharmaceutical industry, regulatory authorities, Health Technology Assessment (HTA) bodies, reimbursement agencies, academics, health care professionals, patients and patient organizations) on how and when patient preference studies (PPS) should be performed, as well as how the results of these PPS can be used to inform the decision-making process along the MPLC.

The PREFER project consists of four work packages (WPs), that are divided into several tasks. WP1 covers overall project management, dissemination, and communication activities as well as data management. WP2 sought to understand stakeholder concerns, needs and insights regarding the use of PPS, aiming to recommend the use of specific methodologies for the case studies in WP3. WP3 designed, executed and evaluated the case studies of this project. Three disease areas were initially selected by PREFER for the case studies: rheumatoid arthritis (RA), neuromuscular diseases (NMD), and lung cancer. These three disease areas were selected as they span the PREFER criteria matrix for the inclusion of case studies (e.g., involve patients in different age groups, with diseases with different disease severity, treated by drugs that are relatively cheap or expensive). Additionally, several case studies from academia and industry were included into the set of PREFER case studies. Finally, in WP4 the PREFER recommendations regarding when and how to measure patient preference along the MPLC by the different stakeholders (industry, regulators, HTA/payers) will be drafted and these recommendations will incorporate the lessons learned from the case studies conducted.

The task 3.8 purpose was to conduct prospective case studies contributed by both industry or academic partners that are additional to the core case studies covering the PREFER selected disease areas.

Methods

This report builds on the report of task 3.2 that describes how the 8 additional case studies were initially selected and reviewed for inclusion in PREFER.

Review procedures

All case studies were approved by the PREFER Steering Committee (SC) after review of the study synopsis. Subsequently, all studies submitted a study protocol, data management plan and statistical analysis plan for further review by the PREFER SC. Case studies led by academic partners further also submitted a budget overview, time planning and resource allocation overview. All documents were completed using standardized templates provided by the WP3 leadership team (Task 3.1). After review (using standardized review checklists; see Appendix 1) and approval of all documents, teams were permitted to move forward with the conduct of their studies.

Conduct and reporting of case studies

Academic case studies teams were asked to meet and report on their progress monthly. During those meetings progress but also lessons learned were discussed. The SC was updated monthly on progress made in the case studies. All case study teams were asked to report on their case study using the case study deliverable template provided by the WP3 leadership team (See Appendix 2). Subsequently, teams were asked to write an extensive abstract of their study. These abstracts are included in this report in order to provide an overview of the case study methods as well as main results.

Results

A full overview of all case studies can be found in the case study portfolio (Appendix 3). The full reports on each of the case studies are documented separately. Below, a high-level overview of the 8 case studies is provided.

Content of the case studies per decision point of the MPLC

Table 1 describes which of the decision point in the MPLC are addressed in each of the case studies.

Table 1. Overview of the MPLC decision points and which case studies are addressing them.

		Studies
Industry decision points	Select & prioritize targets and leads*	-
	Prioritize studies	-
	Prioritize assets (phase 2)	-
	Optimize & prioritize assets (phase 3)*	Myocardial infarction
	Regulatory submission and launch	-
	Manage product lifecycle*	Diabetes
Regulatory decision Making		Chronic pain, Rheumatoid Arthritis, Multiple Myeloma
HTA/reimbursement decision making		COPD, Haemophilia (both)

*These decision points were addressed by one of the PREFER core case studies.

Content of the case studies per prioritized methodological research question

Table 2 describes which PREFER prioritized research questions were addressed in each of the case studies.

Table 2. Overview of PREFER priority research questions and which additional case studies address them

	priority questions 1.2 & 1.3 (2d & 2d1) Comparing methods	priority question 1.4 & 1.5 & 1.6 (2e & 2e2) Impact of changes in the number, type and definitions of attributes	priority question 1.14 (9b) Generalizability of preferences across populations?	priority question 1.16 (7d) Impact of educational material on understanding and preferences	priority question 1.19 (10b1) Can psychosocial constructs provide insight regarding an individual's preferences	priority question 1.10 (4b1) What tests assess whether patients can perform a given set of cognitive tasks?	priority question 1.11(5b): What approach can be used to determine which patient preference method to use for a given circumstance?
Industry-led studies							
Myocardial infarction	X				X		
Chronic pain	X		X		X	X	X
COPD			X		X	X	
Hemophilia					X	X	
Academic-led studies							
Diabetes	X		X	X	X		
Hemophilia					X		X
Multiple myeloma	X		X		X		
Rheumatoid arthritis				X	X		

Summary of each case study

Myocardial infarction

Therapeutic Area	Myocardial Infarction
Core Case Study, Academic Case Study, Industry Case Study	Industry Case Study
Academic Lead, Industry Lead, Methods Lead, Clinical Lead	<u>Industry Lead</u> : Cathy Anne Pinto; <u>Academic Lead</u> : N/A; <u>Methods Lead</u> : Tommi Tervonen (Evidera); <u>Clinical Lead</u> : internal therapeutic area consultation only
Title of the Study	Comparing Patient Preferences for Antithrombotic Treatments for Patients Following an Acute Coronary Syndrome and Patients with Chronic Stable Disease
Background/ Study Rationale	Past studies have assessed patient preferences for antithrombotic treatments in the secondary prevention of cardiovascular disease (CVD) in terms of their benefit and risk characteristics, such as reduction of mortality probability and increases in the probability of non-fatal bleedings. These preferences may differ based on patient characteristics. Currently, no data exists on how patient preferences differ based on disease stage (acute or chronic), and little is known regarding other clinical and demographic factors that may cause preference heterogeneity among patients who have previously experienced a myocardial infarction (MI).
MPLC Decision-making	<u>Main stakeholder (industry, regulatory, HTA)</u> : industry <u>MPLC decision point of interest</u> : clinical development (optimize and prioritize assets)
Clinical Research Questions	How generalizable preferences are from one stage of disease to another? Is there preference heterogeneity based on other demographic and clinical characteristics?
	<u>Question 11j</u> . To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with longitudinal sampling: General population, treatment naïve, shortly after treatment, after chronic treatment, etc.?

Methodological Research Questions	Question 11a. To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with characteristics of patients?
	Question 2d1. How similar are the results from different methods applied with the same set of attributes on the same population? How similar are the results of simpler / faster / cheaper methods vs. more rigorous / in depth / expensive methods?
	Question 10b2. Can the measurement of psychological constructs including health literacy and numeracy provide insight regarding individual preferences?
Study Design	This study was divided into three phases: (i) qualitative pilot; (ii) quantitative pilot; and (iii) main survey. The primary instrument of preference elicitation in the survey was a discrete choice experiment (DCE) task, and the secondary instrument was a best-worst scaling type 1 (BWS-1) task.
	<u>Educational materials:</u> Written materials only
	<u>Psychosocial constructs:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health literacy: Chew Health literacy screening questions • Numeracy: based on Lipkus expanded numeracy scale items
Study Population	<p>This study involved adults (≥ 18 years of age) who have experienced their most recent MI, either in the past year (≤ 365 days, acute stratum) or more than a year (> 365 days, chronic stratum) ago.</p> <p>Patients meeting the following criteria were enrolled in the study:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 18 years of age • Previously hospitalized with MI: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ within a year of enrolment (acute MI group) ○ more than one year prior to enrolment (chronic MI group) • Able to read and understand English • Willing and able to complete an online survey • Willing and able to provide (electronic) consent to participate in study • Resident of England • For qualitative pilot only: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Willing and able to participate in a telephone interview, and be audio recorded <p>Patients who met the following criteria were excluded:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have a cognitive impairment, hearing difficulty, visual impairment, acute psychopathology, or insufficient knowledge of English that—in the opinion of the investigator/interviewer—could interfere with a patient’s ability to provide written consent and complete an interview or survey. • Are pharmaceutical employees and those employed in a position where they have a direct role in treating patients with an MI.

	<p>In this study, 10 patients with chronic MI participated in the qualitative pilot while an additional 40 patients with chronic MI participated in the quantitative pilot. In the main survey, a total of 335 patients were recruited, of which n=180 were patients with chronic MI and n=155 were patients with acute MI.</p>		
<p>Exposure & Outcome</p>	<p>This study assessed the preferences of MI patients for antithrombotic treatment attributes using cross-sectional survey methodology. As such, there was no assignment of patients to a therapeutic strategy or use of any diagnostic or monitoring process for participation in or during the study. The primary outcome obtained from the DCE and BWS was the estimated marginal utilities of the treatment attributes and levels. Subsequently, the relative attribute importance (RAI) was computed from the estimated marginal utilities as the secondary outcome measure to facilitate comparison between DCE and BWS. In addition, estimated marginal utilities from the DCE were used to calculate the maximum acceptable risk (MAR) of cardiovascular death that patients were willing to accept for a reduction of other risks.</p>		
<p>Study Setting</p>	<p>Patients with chronic MI were recruited from online patient panels for the qualitative and quantitative pilot phase between February-May 2018 (qualitative pilot) and July 2018 (quantitative pilot) respectively. For the main survey, patients with chronic MI were recruited from online patient panels; while patients with acute MI were recruited by clinicians and research staff at five participating UK National Health Service (NHS) clinical sites. The NHS clinical sites involved in the study were: Kent Community Health NHS Trust, University Hospitals Plymouth NHS Trust, Chesterfield Royal Hospital NHS Foundation Trust and Imperial College Healthcare NHS Trust. Recruitment for patients with chronic MI for the main survey occurred in February 2019 and recruitment of patients with acute MI from the NHS sites took place between February 2019 and May 2020. Ethical approval for this study was received from the research ethics committee (REC) and health research authority (HRA) on 25 January 2018. Findings from the pilot studies were used to update the survey instrument. An approval for the amendments was sought from the REC/HRA, with approval for the main survey data collection received on 10 December 2018.</p>		
<p>Statistical Methods</p>	<p>Descriptive statistics were used to summarize patients' sociodemographic and clinical characteristics. DCE responses collected from the survey were analyzed using discrete choice models based on random utility maximization (RUM) theory. Multinomial logit (MNL) was estimated for the combined sample (both acute and chronic MI patients) and for the acute and chronic patient subgroups. In addition, mixed logit (MXL), latent class (LC), and heteroscedastic logit (HMNL) models were estimated separately for the combined sample. Responses from the BWS were analyzed using MNL model.</p>		
<p>Results</p>	<p>PREFER Clinical and Methodologic Research Questions</p>	<p>How was it addressed in this preference study</p>	<p>What was found</p>
	<p>Clinical Questions:</p>		
	<p>Overlap with methodologic</p>	<p>see below</p>	<p>see below</p>

	<p>questions 11j and 11a.</p>						
<p>Methodological Questions:</p>							
	<p><u>Question 11j.</u> To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with longitudinal sampling: General population, treatment naïve, shortly after treatment, after chronic treatment, etc.?</p>	<p>In order to assess the effect of stage of MI in patients’ preferences for anti-thrombotics, this study administered a DCE survey to two independent group of patients who differed in their duration since most recent MI (i.e. acute MI patients defined as those with their most recent MI within the year (≤ 365 days) prior to study enrolment and chronic MI patients defined as those enrolled more than one year (>365 days) after experiencing their most recent MI).</p>	<p>In order to test the presence of any systematic difference in preferences between patients with acute and chronic MI, interaction effects between MI duration (acute vs chronic) and the attributes were included in the MNL model. This study demonstrated that patients’ preferences for anti-thrombotic treatment are similar between patients with acute and chronic. Patients with acute and chronic MI valued reduction in risk of CV death ($\beta_{Acute}=0.156$ vs. $\beta_{Chronic}=0.156-0.021=0.135$, p-value=0.319), heart attack ($\beta_{Acute}=0.078$ vs. $\beta_{Chronic}=0.078+0.009=0.087$, p-value=0.552), stroke ($\beta_{Acute}=0.071$ vs. $\beta_{Chronic}=0.071-0.020=0.051$, p-value=0.660), bleeding within the skull ($\beta_{Acute}=0.222$ vs. $\beta_{Chronic}=0.222-0.039=0.183$, p-value=0.205), and other severe bleeding ($\beta_{Acute}=0.142$ vs. $\beta_{Chronic}=0.142+0.020=0.162$, p-value=0.463) similarly.</p>				
	<p><u>Question 11a.</u> To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with characteristics of patients?</p>	<p>The effect of individual characteristics on patients’ preference for anti-thrombotic was explored using subgroup analysis for the following characteristics:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="640 1182 1193 1377"> <thead> <tr> <th>Characteristics</th> <th>Category</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Disease stage</td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> chronic, acute 0–6 months since M or acute 6–12 months since MI </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Characteristics	Category	Disease stage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> chronic, acute 0–6 months since M or acute 6–12 months since MI 	<p>Patients who were 65 years old and above valued reduction in risk of heart attack more than patients who are below 65 years old ($\beta_{Above\ 65}=0.066+0.032=0.097$ vs. $\beta_{Below\ 65}=0.066$, p-value=0.035). Meanwhile, patients without any bleeding risk factor valued reduction in risk of cardiovascular death ($\beta_{No\ bleeding\ risk\ factor}=0.184$ vs. $\beta_{Bleeding\ risk\ factor\ \geq 1}=0.184+(-0.060)=0.125$, p-value=0.006) and heart attack ($\beta_{No\ bleeding\ risk\ factor}=0.114$ vs. $\beta_{Bleeding\ risk\ factor\ \geq 1}=0.114+(-0.047)=0.067$, p-</p>
Characteristics	Category						
Disease stage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> chronic, acute 0–6 months since M or acute 6–12 months since MI 						

		Bleeding risk factors (<i>low body weight, prior use of antithrombotic medications, prior CVD</i>)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> no risk factor ≥1 risk factors 	value=0.005) more than patients who have at least one bleeding risk factor. On the other hand, patients who are at high risk of developing future ischaemic event (as quantified by TIMI risk score of ≥3) valued risk of cardiovascular death less than patients who are at low risk (TIMI risk score ≤ 1) ($\beta_{\text{TIMI score} \geq 3} = 0.149 + (-0.073) = 0.076$ vs. $\beta_{\text{TIMI score} \leq 1} = 0.149$, p-value=0.011).
		Prior health outcomes of interest, other than MI (<i>stroke, ICH, other major bleeding/hemorrhage</i>)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> no prior outcome ≥1 prior outcomes 	
		More than one MI in the past	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> no yes 	
		Prior family member or close friend with health outcomes of interest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> no yes 	
		Age	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <65 years ≥65years 	
		Gender	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> male female 	
		Risk of future ischaemic event based on TIMI score	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low score ≤1) (TIMI 	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medium (TIMI score=2) • High (TIMI score ≥3) <p>The statistical testing of the presence of any systematic difference in preferences in the abovementioned subgroups was done by introducing interaction effects between the observable characteristics and the attributes in a MNL model, for one subgroup at a time.</p>	
	<p><u>Question 2d1.</u> How similar are the results from different methods applied with the same set of attributes on the same population? How similar are the results of simpler / faster / cheaper methods vs. more rigorous / in depth / expensive methods?</p>	<p>In order to explore how different preference elicitation method may impact on the reporting of preferences, this study compared the use of DCE and BWS-1 to elicit patients' preference for anti-thrombotic.</p>	<p>The estimated coefficients from the MNL models for the DCE and BWS cannot be compared directly due to differences in scale. As such the estimated coefficients were used to compute the relative importance of attributes.</p> <p>In the DCE, the most important attribute for patients was reducing the risk of cardiovascular death (52.4%; 95% CI 48.9 - 55.9), followed by risk of heart attack (18.2%; 95% CI 15.6 – 20.8], risk of bleeding within the skull (14.9%; 95% CI 12.7 – 17.0), risk of other form of severe bleeding (11.2%; 95% CI 9.3 – 13.0) and stroke (3.3%, 95% CI 1.1 – 5.4).</p> <p>In the BWS, patients cared most about avoiding cardiovascular death ($\beta=2.943$ (SE 0.141)) followed by stroke ($\beta=0.163$ (SE 0.68)), heart attack ($\beta=-0.489$ (SE 0.068)), bleeding within the skull ($\beta=-0.492$ (SE 0.063)) and other form of severe bleeding ($\beta=-2.125$ (SE 0.085)).</p> <p>Comparison between DCE and BWS-1 showed difference in how patients valued the importance of the treatment attributes/ outcomes particular for prevention of stroke. This difference is likely to be due to</p>

			<p>the different underlying decision-making process between DCE and BWS-1 in this study. In the BWS-1, patients were asked to indicate the most and least important outcome to avoid without information on the risks of developing the outcomes. While in the DCE, they were asked to indicate their preferred treatment choice based on varying level of risks for each attribute.</p>
	<p><u>Question 10b2</u>. Can the measurement of psychological constructs including health literacy and numeracy provide insight regarding individual preferences?</p>	<p>In this study, the effect of patients' subjective health literacy and numeracy skills on their preferences for anti-thrombotic treatments were explored using latent class model. Following identification of different classes/groups of preferences with the latent class model, the probability of belonging to the different classes was analyzed as a function of the patients' observable characteristics as well as their subjective health literacy and numeracy skills in a MNL model.</p>	<p>Based on the DCE responses, the latent class model identified two distinct classes of preferences. Class 1 contains approximately 28% of the sample population. Patients in class 1 did not have any significant preferences for changes in risk of cardiovascular death and heart attack. Their choices were mainly driven by changes in risk of bleeding within the skull, other severe bleeding and stroke. Meanwhile, approximately 72% of the sample population falls into class 2. Their choices were mainly driven by changes in risk of cardiovascular death. Individuals characteristics that influence class membership were explored using a MNL regression model. Only presence of bleeding risk factors and health numeracy skill was were found to significantly contribute to class allocation. Patients with at least one bleeding risk factor were more likely to fall into Class 1 compared to patients without any bleeding risk factors. In addition, patients who have inadequate level of health numeracy skills were more likely to fall into Class 1 compared to</p>

		patients with adequate level of health numeracy skills.
Conclusions	This study demonstrated that patients’ preferences for anti-thrombotic treatment are similar between patients with acute and chronic MI. Consistent with the findings in existing literature, there was a large variability in patients’ preferences for anti-thrombotic treatment across patients which can be explained in part by their sociodemographic and clinical characteristics. This study also showed that different elicitation method may affect reporting of preferences due to different underlying decision-making process. Future research comparing DCE and BWS methods is warranted.	
Limitations	The study compared preferences between patients with acute and chronic MI using data obtained from two independent groups of patients and, with this approach, may not be able to account for the variation in individual-specific effect and assess if the same individual would report the same preference over time. Also, the study included key treatment attributes often used in regulatory B-R decision-making and, although patients were asked during the qualitative pilot to identify any additional treatment attributes that were important, no separate qualitative research was conducted to identify and formulate attributes of importance to patients in advance of this study.	
Potential Use of Results in MPLC Decision-Making	Understanding preference heterogeneity by disease stage is of particular relevance for antithrombotic drugs as they are investigated and approved for initial administration at different stages of the disease process, including acute (at the point of hospitalization) and chronic phases of disease, with the probability of future events increasing dramatically within the first several months of the acute event and plateauing in more chronic phases. Knowledge of whether acute and chronic patients have different preferences (i.e., willingness to accept higher probability of side effects in exchange for higher efficacy) can inform different decision-making processes during the medial product lifecycle. For e.g., if a pharmaceutical company simultaneously brings two products through early phases of development including one that is administered during the acute period of hospitalization and a second during more chronic phases of disease, then differences regarding tolerability of side effects can impact go-no go decisions for one or both products as each drug enters different phases of drug development. During prioritization of assets, prescribing preferences are often assessed, but patient preferences are not a common perspective taken into consideration during these earlier phases of drug development. Challenging portfolio trade-off decisions must be made if the investment needed to initiate later phases of development affects other projects in the portfolio competing for resources. Approximately two thirds of the drug candidates entering Phase 3 will successfully advance to regulatory submission in about two and a half years. Given drugs are approved by regulators for use during more chronic and acute phases of disease, understanding differences in tolerability of patients could also inform benefit-risk decision-making processes to determine marketing authorization.	
Transferability	When patient preferences are used to inform clinical or policy decisions, it is important to know whether the elicited preferences also represent the views of the relevant population, and if they are transferable to other, similar indications, or countries of interest. The extent to which DCE results are generalizable depends on the indication as well as the study population ¹ . The patient sample in the current study was similar to	

populations in other CVD studies conducted both in the UK and in other countries: there were more males with similar age distribution and co-morbidities². Although we recruited from two different sources (NHS clinics and panels) patients who were at different stages of MI (acute or chronic), neither error variance nor preferences were found to significantly differ between the two subgroups. This suggests that our results may be generalizable to the UK MI patient population, and possibly to other countries as well. At present, there is limited evidence on how patient preferences on antithrombotic therapies may be transferrable between indications, such as between patients who have experienced MI and patients who have experienced a stroke. A systematic review found that patient preferences for different patient populations (e.g. venous thromboembolism, acute MI or stroke) and alternative approaches to antithrombotic therapies appear to be highly variable³, but whether this is due to procedural or sampling variance is not known. A number of factors may explain the variability in preferences within and across studies. Based on the review, the authors suggest that future studies eliciting patient preference should include recruitment of patients who have not previously made the choices under investigation. Although prior experiences may result in a better understanding of the treatment under consideration, it may introduce factors other than preferences for the health states described in their responses (particularly cognitive dissonance). Second, in order to gain a better understanding of whether differing health state descriptions significantly affect health state valuations, future research may test the impact of different descriptions on participant valuations. Ideally, standard descriptions of bleed and stroke outcomes would be developed and applied across studies. Finally, research should ensure that participants understand the preference elicitation exercise and explore factors that bear significantly on patient decisions. Transferability across different patient populations requires further exploration and study replication using common preference elicitation methods to improve the current understanding of whether preferences obtained from patients with one indication for antithrombotic drugs transfers to patients with other forms of atherothrombotic disease.

References:

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Chronic pain

Therapeutic Area	Chronic pain associated with osteoarthritis (OA) and/or chronic low back pain (CLBP)
Core Case Study, Academic Study, Industry Study	Industry Case Study
Academic Lead, Industry Lead, Methods Lead, Clinical Lead	Industry Leads: Leo Russo (Pfizer), Kristin Bullok (Lilly), and Brett Hauber (Pfizer)
Title of the Study	Patient preference for osteoarthritis pain and chronic low back pain treatment in the United States and United Kingdom
Background/ Study Rationale	Pfizer and Eli Lilly were developing tanezumab, a novel treatment for chronic pain. Tanezumab, a nonopioid analgesic administered subcutaneously every 8 weeks, was investigated in difficult-to-treat patients with moderate-to-severe knee and hip OA or CLBP with inadequate treatment response —or intolerance—to prior treatment with three classes of pain treatment. Tanezumab is a long-acting, injectable treatment that differs from currently available treatments in its mechanism of action, duration of effect, and mode of administration. Tanezumab is not associated with adverse events (AEs) such as the physical dependence seen with opioids or heart attack risk seen with NSAIDs. However, the unique mechanism of action of NGF inhibition may result in tanezumab causing musculoskeletal and neurological AEs. A patient preference study was designed to understanding the preferences of patients with moderate-to-severe OA or CLBP for chronic pain treatment attributes that are important to them and that might differentiate tanezumab from other chronic pain treatments. Separate preference studies were conducted in the US and United Kingdom (UK) using the same survey instrument.
MPLC Decision-making	Main stakeholder (industry, regulatory, HTA): Regulatory MPLC decision-point of interest: Market Authorization
Clinical Research Questions	The overall objective of this study was to quantify patients' preferences for attributes of pharmaceutical treatments for chronic moderate-to-severe musculoskeletal pain associated with OA and/or CLBP that are both relevant to patients and that differentiate tanezumab from alternative classes of analgesics (including NSAIDs and opioids), and other NGF-inhibitor products, and to quantify both the relative importance of each of these treatment attributes to patients and the tradeoffs patients are willing to make among these attributes. A secondary objective of this study was to explore heterogeneity in preferences for nine subgroups. Preferences were analyzed for prespecified subgroups of interest to identify systematic differences in the preferences of different types of respondents.

Methodological Research Questions	<p>How similar are the results from different methods applied with the same set of attributes on the same population? (IMI-PREFER Question 2d)</p> <p>How generalizable are preferences from one specific population in a disease to different populations in that disease or related diseases? (IMI-PREFER Question 9b)</p> <p>What tests assess whether patients can perform a given set of cognitive tasks? (IMI PREFER Question 4b1)</p> <p>Are there certain properties of a preference problem that indicate a certain method works better than others? (IMI-PREFER Question 5b1)</p> <p>Can the measurement of psychosocial constructs including PREFER class I constructs (health literacy and numeracy, patient activation, and health locus of control) and class II constructs (self-efficacy, treatment-related beliefs, illness perception, and risk propensity) provide insight regarding preference heterogeneity (i.e., how much of the heterogeneity of preference studies can be explained by different results in particular psychological instruments)? (IMI-PREFER Question 10b3)</p> <p>To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with “Characteristics of patients?” (Question 11a)</p>
Study Design	<p>Overall: The study involved the development, administration, and analysis of a stated-preference survey instrument for patients with moderate-to-severe OA only, moderate-to-severe CLBP only, and concurrent moderate-to-severe OA and CLBP in the UK to elicit preferences for treatment attributes that were previously identified as being important to patients and that potentially differentiate tanezumab from other analgesics. The survey included a discrete-choice experiment (DCE) to elicit patients’ preferences for a primary set of treatment attributes and an object-case best-worst scaling (BWS-1) exercise to elicit patients’ assessment of the relative importance of additional relevant treatment attributes that could not be included in the DCE because of the limit on the number of attributes in the DCE. The attributes in the DCE and BWS were the same for patients with OA only, CLBP only, and concurrent OA and CLBP.</p> <p>The attributes included in the DCE were symptom control, incremental treatment-related risk of severe rapidly progressive joint problems requiring total joint replacement, which was intended to capture the risk of rapidly progressive osteoarthritis (RPOA) and was described to patients using the label “risk of severe joint problems,” risk of heart attack, risk of physical dependency, mode and frequency of administration, and personal (out-of-pocket) cost per month. The three harm attributes in the DCE were chosen to capture the most severe event for each of the three treatment classes of interest (i.e., NGF inhibitors, NSAIDS, and opioids). The attributes included in the BWS were risk of moderate-to-severe constipation while taking a medicine, risk of feeling foggy and drowsy while taking a medicine, risk of having a bleeding stomach ulcer when first starting a medicine, risk of mild-to-moderate nausea and vomiting while taking a medicine, risk each year of having a heart attack because of a medicine, risk each year of severe joint problems because of a medicine, risk each year of becoming physically dependent on a prescription pain medicine, risk of having a tingling or burning sensation in the fingers or toes while taking a medicine, risk of mild-to-moderate</p>

	<p>swelling in the ankles and feet while taking a medicine, and risk each year of having a moderate stroke because of a medicine.</p> <p>In addition to the DCE and BWS questions, the survey included written descriptions of each attribute and level included in the DCE, questions designed to assess patients’ comprehension of the attributes and choice tasks, questions about respondents’ experiences using treatments for moderate-to-severe OA pain and CLBP, an assessment of respondent locus of control using the Multidimensional Health Locus of Control (MHLC) Scale – Form C (Wallston et al., 1994), and questions regarding respondents’ demographic characteristics. The survey instruments differed between conditions (i.e., OA pain only, CLBP only, and concurrent OA and CLBP) only where necessary in the questions developed to elicit disease and treatment experience.</p> <p>Educational materials: None</p> <p>Psychosocial constructs: Multidimensional Health Locus of Control (MHLC) Scale – Form C (Wallston et al., 1994),</p>
Study Population	<p>Respondents were residents of the UK or US and were aged 18 years or older with a self-reported physician diagnosis of hip or knee OA only, CLBP only, or concurrent OA and CLBP, each diagnosed at least 3 months ago; with self-reported moderate-to-severe pain in the hip, knee, and/or lower back, each defined as a self-assessed rating of 5 or greater on average in the past week on an 11-point numeric pain scale ranging from 0 (no pain) to 10 (worst possible pain); and who had taken or tried (1) three or more classes of pain treatment in the past 2 years; (2) two prior classes of pain treatment, either excluding NSAIDs due to NSAID contraindication or excluding opioids due to the respondent’s unwillingness to take opioids; or (3) one prior class of pain treatment excluding NSAIDs due to NSAID contraindication and excluding opioids due to the respondents’ unwillingness to take opioids. For respondents with concurrent OA pain and CLBP, a self-assessed pain rating of 5 or greater (of 10) was required for either OA pain or CLBP for the respondent to be eligible. Respondents were able to read and understand English and provide informed consent.</p> <p>The recruitment goal was to have approximately one-third of respondents with pain due to OA only, approximately one-third of respondents with CLBP only, and approximately one-third of respondents with concurrent OA pain and CLBP. A second recruitment goal was that approximately half of the respondents were currently taking or had tried within the past 2 years an opioid to treat OA pain and/or CLBP. Respondents were recruited from an existing Internet panel.</p>
Exposure & Outcome	<p>The variables captured in the online survey included demographic and disease- and treatment-experience variables, assessments of respondent comprehension of the treatment attributes and DCE questions, items included in the MHLC Scale – Form C, and responses to the DCE and BWS questions.</p>
Study Setting	<p>This study involved primary data collection using a self-administered online survey instrument. The data were collected using a nationwide patient panel from 21 February 2019 to 15 April 2019.</p>

<p>Statistical Methods</p>	<p>Descriptive variables and items included in the MHLC Scale – Form C were analyzed using STATA 15 (Stata Corp, College Station, TX). Random-parameters logit (RPL) models were used to analyze the DCE and BWS data from the sample. Exploratory LC analysis was also conducted on the DCE data. Data from the DCE and BWS questions were analyzed independently. Each RPL model of the DCE data yielded a set of relative preference weights for the attribute levels included in the DCE survey. The results of the RPL model of the DCE data were used to calculate the conditional relative importance of each attribute included in the DCE and the marginal rates of substitution between pairs of attributes. Each RPL model of the BWS data yielded a set of relative importance estimates for the attributes included in the BWS exercise. Analyses of the DCE and BWS data were conducted using STATA 15 (Stata Corp, College Station, TX). All quantitative estimates were presented with 95% confidence intervals (CIs). Sub-group comparisons were made using a joint test of significance that tested all interaction terms capturing differences between subgroups for all attribute levels. The difference tested was whether all terms were jointly significantly different from zero, commonly referred to as “statistically significantly systematically different”.</p>		
<p>Results</p>	<p>PREFER Research Questions</p>	<p>How was it addressed in this preference study</p>	<p>What was found</p>
	<p>How similar are the results from different methods applied with the same set of attributes on the same population? (IMI-PREFER Question 2d)</p>	<p>The pain preference study included both a discrete-choice experiment (DCE) and a Case 1 best-worst scaling (BWS-1) exercise. The DCE was the primary preference elicitation method in this study. The BWS exercise was included to allow us to elicit preference information on a number of adverse events related to pain treatments that could not be accommodated in the DCE because of the effective limit on the number of attributes that can be included in a DCE. As noted above, the BWS exercise was not included to answer the same question as the DCE. That is, the attributes in the DCE and the attributes in the BWS were not the same. Because the full set of attributes differs between the DCE and BWS exercises, we were not be able to directly compare</p>	<p>US study: <i>Rank Order:</i> The rank order of the conditional relative importance of the risks included in both the DCE and the BWS was consistent between the methods: 25% risk of physical dependence was the most important of these three risks. 0.5% risk of heart attack was the second most important of these risks. 4% risk of severe joint damage was the least important of these risks. <i>Statistically Significant Differences in Importance:</i> In the DCE, the conditional relative importance of a 25% risk of physical dependence was statistically significantly greater than the conditional relative importance of a 0.5% risk of heart attack; however,</p>

		<p>the two methods as suggested in the research question.</p> <p>However, to provide a link between the attributes in the DCE and the attributes in the BWS, three risk attributes were included in both exercises. Specifically, the highest level of each risk attribute included in the DCE was also included in the BWS exercise (4% risk of severe joint damage, 25% risk of physical dependence, and 0.5% risk of heart attack).</p> <p>Therefore, we were able to compare the rank ordering of these three attributes between the two exercises and assess qualitatively the consistency of the conditional relative importance estimates for these attributes between the two exercises.</p>	<p>the conditional relative importance of a 0.5% risk of heart attack was not statistically significantly greater than the conditional relative importance of a 4% risk of severe joint damage. In contrast, in the BWS, the relative importance of a 25% risk of physical dependence was not statistically significantly greater than the conditional relative importance of a 0.5% risk of heart attack, but the conditional relative importance of a 0.5% risk of heart attack was statistically significantly greater than the conditional relative importance of a 4% risk of severe joint damage.</p> <p><i>Ratios of Relative Importance:</i> In addition, the ratios among these three risks differed substantially between the two exercises. Specifically, in the DCE (BWS) a 25% risk of physical dependence was 4.3 (1.1) times as important as a 0.5% risk of heart attack, a 25% risk of physical dependence was 6.3(1.5) times as important as a 4% risk of severe joint damage, and a 0.5% risk of heart attack was 1.5 (1.4) times as important as a 4% risk of severe joint damage.</p> <p>UK study: <i>Rank Order:</i> The rank order of the conditional relative importance of the risks included in both the DCE and the</p>
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			<p>BWS was inconsistent between the methods. In the DCE, 25% risk of physical dependence was the most important of these three risks. 0.5% risk of heart attack was the second most important of these risks. 4% risk of severe joint damage was the least important of these risks. In the BWS, 0.5% risk of heart attack was the most important of these three risks. 25% risk of physical dependence was the second most important of these risks. 4% risk of severe joint damage was the least important of these risks.</p> <p><i>Statistically Significant Differences in Importance:</i></p> <p>As noted above, the rank order of the conditional relative importance of a 25% risk of physical dependence and a 0.5% risk of heart attack differed between the DCE and the BWS. In both exercises, the conditional relative importance estimates for 25% risk of dependence and 0.5% risk of heart attack were statistically significantly different. However, in the DCE, the conditional relative importance of a 0.5% risk of heart attack (ranked 2nd) and the conditional relative importance of a 4% risk of severe joint problems (ranked 3rd) were not statistically significantly different. In contrast, in the BWS, the conditional relative importance of a 25% risk of dependence (ranked 2nd) was</p>
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			<p>statistically significantly greater than the conditional relative importance of a 4% risk of severe joint damage (ranked 3rd).</p> <p><i>Ratios of Relative Importance:</i> As noted above, the rank order of the conditional relative importance of a 25% risk of physical dependence and a 0.5% risk of heart attack differed between the DCE and the BWS. Therefore, the ratios of the conditional relative importance estimated of these two differed between the two exercises. specifically, in the DCE (BWS), a 25% risk of physical dependence was 7.4 (1.3) times as important as a 4% risk of severe joint damage and a 0.5% risk of heart attack was 1.6 (1.6) times as important as a 4% risk of severe joint problems.</p>
	<p>What tests assess whether patients can perform a given set of cognitive tasks? (IMI-PREFER Question 4b1)</p>	<p>The survey included 7 questions to assess respondents' comprehension in three specific areas: comprehension of the attribute descriptions, comprehension of the risk presentation, and comprehension of the DCE questions. We calculated the frequency with which respondents answered each comprehension question incorrectly and tested for whether respondents who answered three or more comprehension questions incorrectly had statistically significantly systematically different preference estimates than those who answer less than three comprehension questions incorrectly.</p>	<p>We found statistically significantly different preference estimates between respondents who answered 3 or more comprehension questions incorrectly and respondents who answered less than 3 comprehension questions incorrectly in both the UK and the US.</p> <p>In the US, the preference estimates and conditional relative importance estimates for those respondents who answered 3 or more comprehension questions incorrectly were very similar to those for respondents who answered less</p>

		<p>It is important to note that if a respondent answered a comprehension question incorrectly, the correct answer to the comprehension question was provided prior to the respondent proceeding with the survey. Therefore, an incorrect response to a comprehension question does not necessarily indicate that the respondent did not understand the corresponding concept when completing the remainder of the survey.</p>	<p>than 3 comprehension questions incorrectly. The primary differences between the two subgroups was that respondents who answered 3 or more comprehension questions incorrectly appear to have placed greater weight on pain control and those who answered less than 3 comprehension questions incorrectly appear to have placed slightly less weight on the risk of severe joint damage. In the UK, the preference estimates and conditional relative importance estimates for those respondents who answered 3 or more comprehension questions incorrectly were noticeably different than for respondents who answered less than 3 comprehension questions incorrectly. Respondents who answered fewer than 3 comprehension questions incorrectly placed noticeably greater weight on pain control and appear to be less averse to heart attack risk than respondents who answered 3 or more comprehension questions correctly.</p>
	<p>Are there certain properties of a preference problem that indicate a certain method works better than others? (IMI-PREFER Question 5b1)</p>	<p>This question was not be addressed directly in this study. However, we had a strong rationale for choosing the methods employed in this study and based this choice on the ability of the method to address the research questions.</p>	<p>We effectively approached this study with two distinct types of research questions. Our primary objective was to estimate the tradeoffs that patients were willing to make between the benefits, risks, and mode and frequency of administration of</p>

			<p>treatment. The treatments under consideration were (or were intended to be) indicated for the same conditions and have the same primary objectives – to reduce pain and improve function. However, the three types of treatment under consideration have substantially different mechanisms of action and each has different adverse events that are of concern to patients, physicians, and regulators. Therefore, the willingness of patients to tolerate these different risks to achieve the same outcome is important. In addition, these treatments vary substantially in their mode and frequency of administration and it is unknown whether patients would be willing to accept additional risk or decreases in expected benefit to have the mode and frequency of administration they prefer. Therefore, the research question was one in which decision makers are essentially asked to trade off multiple attributes simultaneously. Therefore, we believed that this question was best addressed using a discrete-choice experiment. The second objective was to understand where multiple other potential risks fit into patient decision making relative to the major or key risks that were included in the DCE. Because there</p>
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			<p>were many potential risks associated with each of these types of products, conducting a DCE that included all of these risks likely would not have been feasible. Therefore, we chose to use a method that could accommodate a larger number of risks and provide estimates of relative importance, namely a Case 1 best-worst scaling (BWS-1) exercise.</p>
	<p>How generalizable are preferences from one specific population in a disease to different populations in that disease or related diseases? (IMI-PREFER Question 9b)</p>	<p>The sample included patients with related diseases—osteoarthritis only, chronic low back pain, and concomitant osteoarthritis and chronic low back pain. The sample was stratified to include nearly equal representation across all three categories to facilitate subgroup analyses. The results for each of these subgroups were compared. In addition, the sample included patients from the United States and the United Kingdom. Respondents from these different countries were recruited separately using the same inclusion criteria.</p>	<p>In each country, we used the same survey to elicit patient preferences for all three conditions. We believe that this was appropriate because the goals of treatment are the same for all conditions as are the treatment options.</p> <p>In the US, subgroup analysis of the DCE data did not detect statistically significantly systematic differences in preferences among the three conditions. Latent class analysis showed a marginally insignificant ($P = 0.055$) difference in preferences for patients with chronic low back pain only. Subgroup analysis of the BWS data did not detect statistically significantly systematic differences in preferences among the three conditions.</p> <p>In the UK, subgroup analysis of the DCE data did not detect statistically significantly systematic differences in preferences among the three conditions. Latent class analysis showed a marginally insignificant (P</p>

			<p>= 0.065) difference in preferences for patients with chronic low back pain only. Subgroup analysis of the BWS data showed statistically significantly systematic differences in preferences among the three conditions.</p> <p>The results of the DCE suggest that treatment preferences are mostly generalizable across conditions when the goal of treatment and the treatment options under consideration are the same; however, there is weak evidence that there may be systematic differences in preferences based on condition that were not captured in the DCE. In contrast, evidence from the UK suggests that preferences elicited using the Case 1 BWS are not generalizable across conditions.</p>
	<p>Can the measurement of psychosocial constructs including IMI-PREFER Class I constructs (health literacy and numeracy, patient activation, and health locus of control) and Class II constructs (self-efficacy, treatment-related beliefs, illness perception, and risk propensity) provide insight regarding preference heterogeneity (i.e., how much of the heterogeneity of preference studies can</p>	<p>The survey instrument included the Multidimensional Health Locus of Control (MHLC) Scale – Form C. Subgroup analysis was conducted in which mutually exclusive subgroup pairs were defined in three ways: Respondents who were classified as high “internal” locus of control and patients who were classified as low “internal” locus of control (the median score was used to split the sample in those two subgroups) Respondents who were classified as high “change” locus of control and patients who were classified as low “change” locus of control (the median</p>	<p>In the US, subgroup analysis of the DCE data did not detect statistically significantly systematic differences in preferences based on locus of control. Latent class analysis showed no difference in preferences between patients with different levels of locus of control for any of the three types of locus of control. Subgroup analysis of the BWS data showed statistically significantly systematic differences in preferences between patients with high and low levels of locus of control for all three types of locus of control.</p>

	<p>be explained by different results in particular psychological instruments)? (IMI-PREFER Question 10b3)</p>	<p>score was used to split the sample in those two subgroups) Respondents who were classified as high “powerful others” locus of control and patients who were classified as low “powerful others” locus of control (the median score was used to split the sample in those two subgroups).</p>	<p>In the UK, subgroup analysis of the DCE data did not detect statistically significant systematic differences in preferences based on locus of control; however, the difference in preferences between those with high and low “powerful others” locus of control was only marginally insignificant (P = 0.063). Latent class analysis showed no difference in preferences between patients with different levels of locus of control for any of the three types of locus of control. Subgroup analysis of the BWS data showed statistically significant systematic differences in preferences between patients with high and low levels of locus of control for all three types of locus of control.</p>
	<p>To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with “characteristics of patients?” (IMI-PREFER Question 11a)</p>	<p>This study included the following subgroup analyses in addition to the subgroup analyses described above:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respondents with opioid experience in the last 2 years and those without opioid experience in the last 2 years • Patients younger or older than median age in the sample or patients living with chronic pain for more time and less time than the median time in the sample • Respondents with moderate baseline pain and respondents with severe baseline pain in the past week as self-assessed on an 11-point numeric pain scale ranging from 0 (no pain) to 10 (worst possible pain). 	<p>In the US DCE, only patient performance on the comprehension questions was associated with statistically significant systematic differences in preferences in subgroup analysis. In the latent class analysis, prior opioid experience was the only additional patient characteristic that had a statistically significant effect on class membership. In the subgroup analysis of the BWS data, multiple patient characteristics were found to have statistically significant systematic effects in preferences including opioid experience, age,</p>

			<p>time since diagnosis, and baseline level of pain.</p> <p>In the UK DCE, patient age and performance on the comprehension questions were associated with statistically significant systematic differences in preferences in subgroup analysis. Also, in subgroup analysis of the DCE data, systematic differences in preferences based on time since diagnosis were only marginally insignificant ($P = 0.053$). In the latent class analysis, patient age was also a statistically significant predictor of class membership. In the subgroup analysis of the BWS data, multiple patient characteristics were found to have statistically significant systematic effects in preferences including age, time since diagnosis, and baseline level of pain.</p>
Conclusions	<p>In general, respondents in the US & UK on average preferred better symptom control, avoiding risk of treatment-related physical dependency, and taking oral pills daily. Respondents were much less concerned with avoiding an incremental treatment-related risk of heart attack or severe rapidly progressive joint problems requiring total joint replacement. Patients were willing to accept some level of each type of risk to improve pain and symptom control. There was evidence of preference heterogeneity within the sample. These results suggest that patients, on average, would prefer alternative pharmacological treatments for pain to opioids and that patients, on average, would view NGF-inhibitor products as acceptable alternatives to both NSAIDs and opioids, despite the risks associated with NGF-inhibitor medications.</p>		
Limitations	<p>Respondents of the online survey were recruited through a panel used by SSI. Participants were recruited to be panel members via partnerships with loyalty programs, as well as through banner ads, pop-ups and messages on websites, television advertising, and offline recruiting (e.g., telephone recruitment of targeted populations). Patients who chose to be members of such panels may have had preferences that differ from those of the overall population of patients meeting the eligibility criteria. In addition, respondents who chose to respond to the recruitment invitation may have preferences that differ from those who chose not to</p>		

	<p>respond to the recruitment invitation. This may have resulted in potential volunteer bias, leading to an underestimate or overestimate of respondent satisfaction and preferences. Research has shown that results from online stated-preference studies are, in general, not statistically different from those results elicited through face-to-face interviews (Nielsen, 2011; Marta-Pedroso et al., 2007).</p> <p>The diagnosis of hip or knee OA and/or CLBP and chronic moderate-to-severe pain in the hip, knee, or lower back, as well as patient demographics and treatment history, were self-reported. The online survey assessed eligibility based on self-report to a series of screening questions.</p> <p>The study sample included diversity in terms of gender, education, age, and condition. The study sample also included diversity in terms of duration of chronic pain and prior treatment experience; however, there was a lack of diversity with regard to race and ethnicity. The majority of respondents in this sample self-identified as white or Caucasian.</p> <p>Potential information and selection bias introduced by study design may be the result of the recruitment method chosen. Our respondents may be younger and more educated than the actual patient population. Generalizability of the results may be a concern because of selection bias.</p>
<p>Potential Use of Results in MPLC Decision-Making</p>	<p>The tradeoffs between benefits and risks may inform regulatory (i.e., market authorization) decisions.</p>
<p>Transferability</p>	<p>The DCE results appear to be transferable between different countries and similar pain conditions. Transferability between pain conditions may be a result of the similarity between the conditions and the fact that the benefit attribute (pain and symptom control) was not overly specific. The transferability between countries was noted despite the fact that the US and UK have very different healthcare systems.</p> <p>The BWS results do not appear to be generalizable either between conditions or between counties.</p>

COPD

Therapeutic Area	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD)
Core Case Study, Academic Case Study, Industry Case Study	<i>Industry Case Study</i>
Academic Lead, Industry Lead, Methods Lead, Clinical Lead	<u>Industry Leads:</u> Nigel S. Cook, Florian Gutzwiller
Title of the Study	Patient Preferences in Benefit-Risk Assessments during the Drug Life Cycle
Background/ Study Rationale	<p>The measurement of lung function (FEV1) and exacerbations are traditional measures in clinical trial of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). With the exception of shortness of breath, the measurement of symptoms is much less established. However, previous research evaluating patient perspectives in COPD has shown that besides breathlessness and exacerbations, persistent cough, mucus production, sleep disturbance and urinary incontinence are also of great concern for patients. Because patients are impacted daily by excess mucus production, (chronic) cough (which usually occur together) and shortness of breath in addition to downstream impacts on sleep, physical activity, and as urinary leakage (caused by frequent coughing), COPD imposes a substantial burden on patients' lives.</p> <p>To evaluate the preference of COPD patients, Novartis designed a systematic mixed-methods research program. A targeted literature review, social media listening (SML) study and a qualitative online bulletin board (OBB) study informed the design of this quantitative patient preference study using a discrete choice experiment (DCE). The findings from the literature review, SML and OBB studies, alongside evidence from the clinical guidelines and other preference literature/best practice guidelines have been used to inform the identification and development of attributes and levels for the COPD PPS. This PPS sought to quantify the relative importance that patients place on alleviation of excess mucus production, (chronic) cough and shortness of breath in addition to downstream impacts on sleep, physical activity, and as urinary leakage, including exacerbations.</p>

MPLC Decision-making	Main stakeholder (industry, regulatory, HTA): <i>The primary stakeholders for this study are regulators, industry and HTA.</i>
Clinical Research Questions	<p>Study aim: To quantify the preferences of COPD patients regarding symptoms, the impact on their QOL, and evaluate whether preferences vary with certain respondent characteristics.</p> <p>Primary objective: The level of importance which COPD patients place on symptoms such as cough and mucus secretion and consequences thereof, versus more traditional endpoints such as breathlessness and exacerbations. <i>During the conduct of the study the overall strategy changed and therefore the analysis plan was adapted to analyze preference for improvement of excess mucus production, (chronic) cough and shortness of breath in addition to downstream impacts on sleep, physical activity, and as urinary leakage compared to improvement of exacerbations alone.</i></p> <p>Secondary objective: To provide predicted choice probabilities on trade-offs COPD patients are willing to make to achieve desired COPD disease states.</p> <p>Exploratory objectives: To assess how stated preferences may vary according to patient symptomatic burden and disease severity; socio-demographic characteristics and the level of patient 'activation'.</p>
Methodological Research Questions	<p>4b1: What tests assess whether patients can perform a given set of cognitive tasks?</p> <p>10b1: Can psychosocial constructs including PREFER Class I constructs and Class II constructs provide insight regarding an individual's preferences?</p> <p>10c2: Help to show external validity, particularly in conjunction with PRO or related instruments specific to the disease area?</p> <p>11: To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with Characteristics of patients, Stakeholder, (11d) Disease experience or severity, Treatment experience, (11f) Region, (11g) Culture, Healthy vs heaving disease, Time of diagnosis, Longitudinal sampling, Patients recruited through different channels?</p> <p>15b1 Should the attributes in preference studies aiming to inform MA/payer/industry decisions relate to benefits/risks or also to broader aspects related to quality of life/disease/..., ?</p> <p>15b2: What is the impact of including attributes related to the disease/quality of life/price/... on the preferences elicited?</p> <p>15b3: When in the drug development process should preferences be measured for informing MA/payer/industry decisions?</p> <p>15c2: When along the MPLC should a patient preference study be conducted to inform regulators or HTA?</p> <p>17a: What is the optimal approach towards recruitment of participants? What incentives are needed to</p>

Study Design	<p>Qualitative phase: As preparation for this PPS in COPD, a targeted literature review, a SML study (http://doi.org/10.1183/23120541.00128-2018) and a qualitative OBB study (http://doi.org/10.2147/COPD.S202580) were previously conducted. The synthesized findings from the studies, alongside evidence from clinical guidelines and other preference literature/best practice guidelines were used to inform the identification and development of attributes and levels for the COPD PPS.</p> <p>Quantitative phase: The findings from the qualitative research (described in section 2.1), alongside evidence from clinical guidelines and other preference literature/best practice guidelines, were used to inform patient inclusion and exclusion criteria, the identification and development of an attribute and levels (A&L) grid for DCE in this COPD PPS. These input were reviewed by the project team, clinical experts and patient group representatives from 5 countries (British Lung Foundation, UK; COPD Foundation, US; La Fondation du Soufflé, France; Lung Foundation Australia, Australia and J-Breath, Japan) to finalize the design of the PPS comprising three phases. NICE were consulted for scientific advice on the study design and statistical analysis (NICE provides first scientific advice on PPS design). The study design was also informed by the International Society for Pharmacoeconomics and Outcomes Research (ISPOR) taskforce guidelines and FDA guidance documents for design, conduct and analysis of a PPS.</p>
Study Population	<p>Patients were included in the study if they were aged ≥ 40 years at the time of survey with diagnosis of COPD by a healthcare practitioner, had self-reported moderate-to-severe COPD defined as having had ≥ 1 COPD flare-up/exacerbation in the last year (requiring additional treatment with oral corticosteroids and/or antibiotics to manage their chest symptoms, or had to visit the hospital/emergency room due to COPD) along with daily symptoms of cough and excess mucus production. Patients were excluded if they had participated in a COPD patient survey in the past 3 months.</p>
Study Setting	<p>Primary recruitment was conducted via patient support groups and participation was voluntary. Patient groups in the UK, USA, France, and Australia leveraged their patient's network for the patient recruitment. Supplementary recruitment via patient panels was introduced once patient group recruitment was saturated, with participation compensated at fair market value to encourage patient involvement. In Japan, patients were recruited only through patient panels.</p>

<p>Statistical Methods</p>	<p>Data collected from Phase 2 quantitative survey were analysed using IBM SPSS data collection survey reporter software and P-values reported where required. Hierarchical Bayesian analysis with effects-coding parameterization (subject to acceptable model fitting as confirmed by multinomial logistic regression (MNL) was undertaken on the preference data (alternative disease state) to robustly estimate (using Gibbs sampling) the relative value each respondent places on an attribute level (i.e., the part-worth utilities). Interactions between attributes were tested in terms of their contribution to the model, this was measured in terms of significant change in model fit. In order to represent the effect of current treatments (e.g. standard of care: bronchodilator and/or inhaled corticosteroids [ICS]) and future treatments (for alleviating cough and mucus production), sensitivity analysis was conducted. A simulator tool was developed (built in Excel 2016) to predict “preference shares” (expressed as a percentage) for input profiles. Profile scenarios were simulated in which the health state across different attributes were altered from the average patient (“DCE index”), to demonstrate the potential symptom improvement offered, and in turn generate a preference share.</p>		
<p>Results</p>	<p>PREFER Clinical and Methodological Research Questions</p>	<p>How was it addressed in this preference study</p>	<p>What was found</p>
	<p>10b1 Can psychosocial constructs including PREFER Class I constructs and Class II constructs provide insight regarding an individual’s preferences, and 4b1 What tests assess whether patients can perform a given set of cognitive tasks?</p>	<p>We included a series of survey experience questions to determine things such as the ease of understanding, ease of answering, level of interest to the patient.</p>	<p>Results indicate the study was understandable and that they did not have a problem to answer and complete the survey. The qualitative debriefing interviews prior to finalization of the study design also highlighted areas where respondents had difficulty to understand/answer, allowing us to address these points in the final survey questionnaire and provide the necessary information to make it understandable.</p>

	<p>10c2 - Help to show external validity, particularly in conjunction with PRO or related instruments specific to the disease area?</p>	<p>With both general & disease specific PRO instruments.</p>	<p>PRO questionnaires were used including the CASA-Q, and CAT to assess the severity and impact of COPD in drug development studies for COPD, PAM-Q for attitudinal and EQ-5D [3L] - overall health status information for subgroup analysis.</p>
	<p>11 - To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with Characteristics of patients, Stakeholder, Information level of patients, Disease experience or severity, Treatment experience, Region, Culture, Healthy vs heaving disease, Time of diagnosis, Longitudinal sampling, Patients recruited through different channels?</p>	<p>COPD severity was assessed using four variables: 1) self-perceived severity; 2) number of exacerbations in past 12 months that required hospitalization; 3) COPD Assessment Test (CAT) total score and 4) Cough and Sputum Assessment Questionnaire (CASA-Q) total and domain scores. Patient Activation was assessed with the PAM-Q</p>	<p>Overall, preferences were consistent across the three severity groups. Similarly, patient preference results across activation levels were consistent with the overall findings with no evidence of an association of preferences with activation level.</p>
	<p>11d To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with Disease experience or severity?</p>	<p>Patient preferences were analysed per attribute according to disease severity</p>	<p>Patient preferences were consistent across the severity groups.</p>

	<p>11f To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with Region? and 11g To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with Culture?</p>	<p>The purpose of the study was to elicit overall preferences for symptoms, therefore inter-country comparisons were not in our focus. For the purpose of this IMI case study, some results can be given:</p>	<p>Our study spanned 5 countries. Across countries patients placed almost equal importance on shortness of breath, sleep quality and urinary incontinence. Some differences in relative importance did emerge across the countries: shortness of breath was the most important attribute for patients from Australia and France, and sleep quality for patients from Japan. As we did not specifically categorize the participants by culture, we can only reply to this in the context “culture = country”.</p>
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	<p>15b1 Should the attributes in preference studies aiming to inform MA/payer/industry decisions relate to benefits/risks or also to broader aspects related to quality of life/disease/..., ?</p>	<p>Patient Preference Studies can inform in particular three main decision points in the pathway from drug development to clinical use: Early drug development, in particular the identification of relevant endpoints for pivotal clinical trials; Benefit-risk assessment (regulatory approval); HTA (informing value discussions and reimbursement decisions). Our study was specifically designed to inform the decision of which patient-relevant endpoints to select for phase III clinical trials.</p>	<p>The results are being used to support the inclusion of the six tested endpoints (attributes) in the phase III trial design for our development compound in COPD. Additionally they have been used as input to the development of a Core Outcomes Set for COPD (CoreCOPD). In the future it is expected that value discussions with HTA bodies and regulatory discussions of Benefit/Risk will each be conducted against the background of how important different endpoints are to the patient, taking into consideration the novel COPD endpoints (cough, mucus, sleep, incontinence) investigated in this study. The results are also important when considering preference share simulations and clinical profiling to show a beneficial effect of a new product on more than one of the attributes evaluated in this study.</p>
	<p>15b2 - What is the impact of including attributes related to the disease/quality of life/price/... on the preferences elicited?</p>	<p>Prior to doing the DCE exercise, the study respondents performed a profile matching exercise where they were asked using the attribute and level grid to select the level for each attribute which most closely matched their current disease state.</p>	<p>This information served to categorize the clinical status of the patients and also is being used to generate a 'DCE Index' for each patient, which will be used for correlation analysis with EQ-5D scores. Additionally, this exercise served to familiarize patients with the full context of the DCE,</p>

	<p>15b3 - When in the drug development process should preferences be measured for informing MA/payer/industry decisions, and</p> <p>15c2 - When along the MPLC should a patient preference study be conducted to inform regulators or HTA?</p>	<p>n/a</p>	<p>Gaining patient insights by collecting information on their disease experiences and perspectives should be an ongoing process throughout the product development lifecycle and starts in very early development phases. Regulatory authorities also acknowledge the importance of early patient engagement and appreciate and early engagement with authorities on methods to collect patients' insights. Collectively these initiatives should</p>
	<p>17a - What is the optimal approach towards recruitment of participants? What incentives are needed to recruit patients into preference studies?</p>	<p>Our PPS conducted primary recruitment via patient support groups and participation was voluntary.</p>	<p>Patient groups in the UK, US, France, and Australia leveraged their patients' network for the patient recruitment. Supplementary recruitment via patient panels was introduced once patient group recruitment was saturated, with participation compensated at fair market value to encourage patient involvement. In Japan, patients were recruited only through patient panels.</p>
<p>Conclusions</p>	<p>The study showed patient preference studies are a useful way to assess which aspects of a disease matter most to patients. Analysis of changes in preference weights (utilities) for equivalent improvements in cough and mucus combined, are higher (more valued) than those for shortness of breath alone. As a result, if these improvements are included in a health-state preference simulation (with two profiles: A) cough and mucus improved and B) shortness of breath improved) there is a clear preference for the cough and mucus-improved profile. When comparing two profiles A) daily symptoms improved and B) exacerbations improved, there is a clear preference for the daily symptoms improved profile. This study also showed that gathering patients' insights via a structured and systematic approach, is feasible early in the product lifecycle and may benefit decision making by multiple stakeholders.</p>		

Limitations	<p>There are several important limitations to this study, starting with the range of options offered for each attribute. The worst outcome offered for an attribute is “hospitalisation” for the exacerbation attribute. This is possibly introducing a bias:</p> <p>a) Temporal effect</p> <p>a. Hospitalisations due to exacerbations (severe exacerbations) are much less frequent than exacerbations treated with additional medication (moderate exacerbations). This means that over time there is more benefit accrued by treating exacerbations with medications than with hospitalisations. This temporal effect is only implicitly taken into account, in that it is assumed that when patients performed the DCE, they accounted for these temporal differences. The lack of explicit adjustment gives the exacerbation attribute possibly more weight.</p> <p>b. The temporal effect is even larger, when frequency of hospitalisations due to exacerbations are compared to daily impact of e.g. cough and sputum symptoms.</p> <p>b) Range of options offered</p> <p>a. A hospitalisation is the worst possible outcome across all attributes. However, it was only offered as an option for the exacerbation attribute. The results suggest a hierarchy of patient preference to first avoid severe acute events leading to hospitalisation. It is not surprising therefore that patients the highest single weight to this attribute level compared to all others.</p> <p>b. It is also questionable, whether true independence can be assumed for exacerbations, as they represent a worsening of symptoms and are not really a distinct separate entity.</p> <p>Nevertheless, the study was designed based on the assumption that the attributes are operating independently and the research has confirmed that the attributes have been considered independent in the context of its meaning for the conjoint. The study used an orthogonal design to ensure attributes and levels were being tested independently from one another – the important contributions of the individual features can be isolated from the rest of the (possibly confounding) effects presented simultaneously as part of the DCE. But this does not mean that there are no interrelationships and/or influences of one or more attributes on another.</p> <p>It is acknowledged that online surveys have certain limitations, especially in an aging population, however, literature has been published which indicate results are similar with online and other survey administration routes (e.g. pen and paper) in the elderly (van de Looij-Jansen et al 2008; Braekman et al 2018). In our study, there was also no way to ensure that the patients themselves were completing the surveys without additional help e.g. from a caregiver, however, considering these caveats it was felt that an online survey was the optimal approach to maintain robustness and geographical diversity.</p>
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	<p>Another limitation of this study was the diagnosis of the COPD as eligibility criteria, which was patient self-reported. Since patients were recruited through patient groups and patient panels (not physicians) there will be no healthcare professional confirmed diagnosis, eligibility will be determined by patient-reported confirmation that they have received a diagnosis of moderate to severe COPD from a healthcare professional. This does pose the risk of inclusion of patients without a correct COPD diagnosis. To mitigate this, patients were recruited only via closed patient group membership or patient panels and the screening questions ensured patients regularly experience the most common symptoms related to COPD (cough and mucus); however this does assume honest answering of the questions posed, which must be recognised as a limitation to the study.</p> <p>In this study patient recruitment was via COPD/respiratory patient support groups or COPD patient panels, this should ensure correct inclusion into the study, however patients who are registered with support groups or panels for research purposes, may also be more engaged with their disease management, which could influence their preferences. Some caution is therefore warranted in extrapolating these results to the broader COPD patient population or beyond those countries who were part of the study.</p>
<p>Potential Use of Results in MPLC Decision-Making (Optional)</p>	<p>The results are being used to support the decision to include the six tested endpoints (attributes) in the phase III trial design for a new development compound in COPD. Additionally, the results are provided as input to the development of a Core Outcomes Set for COPD (CoreCOPD).</p>

<p>Transferability (Optional)</p>	<p>We believe the results of our COPD patient preference study should have good transferability between countries, also beyond those covered in the study, for the following reasons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The COPD patient preferences study was conducted across 5 countries (US, UK, France, Australia and Japan) with a total sample size of 1050. Hence the sample was robust (with a minimum of 150 patients in any country) and there was geographic and cultural variability in the countries included in the study. • Prior to the initiation of the preference study, we conducted a social media listening study (English language but no country barriers) and an online bulletin board (UK and US), to help in identifying the symptoms most bothersome to patients, to inform the attributes and levels in our quantitative study design. We also conducted a literature survey which was aligned with the results of our own studies. • The discrete choice experiment was designed to study preferences between different disease states, based upon six symptoms of COPD that were shown to be most relevant to patients in previous qualitative research (which spanned the same 5 countries). Thus differences in available treatment options and standards of care across the countries is less likely to influence the results, since the preferences are instead focused on the symptoms of the disease, not on treatment choice. • Whilst some country-specific differences were seen in the study (e.g. in patient activation levels across countries), the preferences data for relative importance of disease symptom attributes was fairly consistent across the 5 countries (see table 5 for estimated model coefficients for each country - the values in bold are NOT significantly different from zero (possibly because the country sample sizes were not large enough for these to show up as significant). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There are some differences between the countries, notably the “cough” attribute for Japan has all its levels not significant. In some other countries some particular attribute levels are not significant. These country differences may be a reflection of certain differences in age or clinical severity of recruited patients in the study between countries. Additionally, the sample size of N = 150 in some countries may have been insufficient to reveal significances. • The general consistency in preferences across countries was further validated by looking at preferences according to disease severity, which showed a consistency for attribute preferences, regardless of patient disease severity. We also investigated relative importance of the attributes between current smokers and never smoked, and between patients with/without concomitant asthma: In both cases, the attribute relative importance data was consistent, regardless of these sub-groupings. • Socio-demographic and educational characteristics of our patient population was collected, but we didn’t specifically look at preferences according to these characteristics. However, we would not expect these profiling characteristics to influence preferences expressed, based on the above results. • Attitudinal differences, e.g. with respect to adherence to medicines, would not be expected to influence the preference data, since we are not looking at preferences for treatments, only at preferences for symptoms. In support of this, the analysis of preferences according to patient activation showed no differences in our study. <p>In summary, we anticipate good transferability of the data from our COPD study to countries beyond those who partook in the study. A preference study of disease symptoms / health states has certain advantages in this regard, as compared to a preference study between treatment options. The development of a Core Outcomes Set for COPD (CoreCOPD) is intended to be of relevance globally, utilizing also input from the current study, of the six symptoms which formed the attributes in the preference study are transferable to other countries. It should be mentioned however that all the countries in our study were developed countries and the study was performed as an online internet survey; hence we cannot conclude that the results would translate to third world countries or to people (e.g. of low educational level) unable to participate in an online survey.</p>
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Haemophilia

Therapeutic Area	ON-GOING CASE STUDY SUMMARY: case study has not been completed Haemophilia Gene Therapy
Core Case Study, Academic Study, Industry Study	Industry Case Study
Academic Lead, Industry Lead, Methods Lead, Clinical Lead	Industry Leads: Jim Thomson (Pfizer) and Brett Hauber (Pfizer)
Title of the Study	Examining the Preferences of People with Haemophilia for Gene Therapy
Background/ Study Rationale	<p>People with haemophilia (PWH) experience various degrees of bleeding, depending on residual coagulation factor levels. Bleeding occurs most commonly in joints, soft tissue, and muscles, causing short-term symptoms (acute bleeding and acute pain) and long-term complications (chronic pain, haemophilia arthropathy, and disability). Acute and chronic complications may dramatically reduce the health-related quality of life (HRQoL) of PWH.</p> <p>Recent gene therapy trials in both hemophilia A and B have reported promising results, which suggest that gene therapy could yield a long-term functional “cure” by changing or replacing the missing/abnormal genes, leading to sustained in vivo Factor VIII or Factor IX production. Gene therapy could be life changing for PWH, relieving them of the daily burden and limitations they currently experience. Currently, Phase 3 trials of gene therapy for haemophilia are in progress, and these novel therapies have the potential to change the landscape of haemophilia management. However, more research is needed to understand the preferences of PWH for gene therapy. Several studies have explored preferences of PWH, physicians and pharmacists for different existing haemophilia treatments using discrete choice experiments. However, these studies have not addressed preferences as gene therapy becomes available.</p> <p>A recent study, the Patient preferences to Assess Value IN Gene therapies (PAVING) study, conducted at the University of Leuven in Belgium, examined how features of standard therapy and gene therapy for haemophilia influence patients’ choices between these therapy options. The qualitative portion of the PAVING study used semi-structured interviews to identify attributes of gene therapy and standard of care that are important to patients. This was conducted to enable better understanding of trade-offs that patients may make when choosing between gene therapy and current standard of care.</p> <p>Further information on patient preferences for gene therapy in the United Kingdom (UK) would provide a clear view of the patient voice and could identify which specific attributes of gene therapy are important to PWH in the UK. These data may be informative in Health Technology Appraisal (HTA) or other</p>

	<p>submissions to the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) for review of gene therapies for PWH. Assessment of haemophilia treatment preferences in PWH is also important as this may help to inform the most appropriate prescribed treatment regimen, which may translate into increased treatment satisfaction and adherence.</p> <p>This study therefore aimed to assess how people with moderate and severe haemophilia (A and B) in the UK value different attributes of treatment, when considering whether to undergo gene therapy.</p>
MPLC Decision-making	<p>Main stakeholder (industry, regulatory, HTA): Industry is leading the study, but impact will also be on regulatory and HTA. Industry, regulatory and HTA bodies can use information from this study to enable understanding of how PWH in the UK value and weigh up different aspects of gene therapy for haemophilia.</p> <p>MPLC decision-point of interest: Regulatory approval and HTA/other decision-making for gene therapy for haemophilia</p>
Clinical Research Questions	<p>Primary objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To determine the preferences of PWH for haemophilia treatments including gene therapy. <p>Secondary objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To define the relative importance of various treatment attributes (e.g. differences in the frequency and modality of therapy). • To examine how individuals trade-off between attributes. • To identify demographic or clinical characteristics of PWH that may explain differential preferences for attributes of treatment.
Methodological Research Questions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To investigate how patient preferences can be used in decision making 2. To understand how patient preference studies can be conducted in rare diseases 3. To investigate differences in preferences with varying levels of disease severity (11d) 4. To investigate how to ensure patient preference information from preference studies is applicable/tailored to HTA/payer decision making (15b)
Study Design	<p>This study is sponsored by Pfizer, with input from collaborators at the University of Leuven.</p> <p>This study is composed of 4 phases:</p> <p>Phase 1 – profile development: targeted literature review and interviews with a group of multiple stakeholders, including patient advocates and clinicians, to identify haemophilia treatment attributes which could be used in a DCE to elicit preferences for gene therapy.</p> <p>The literature review aimed to compile information on characteristics of the therapies for PWH, the attributes and levels used in previous DCE studies in haemophilia, and clinical trials of gene therapies currently underway in haemophilia. This information was used to construct the first proposal of attributes and levels,</p>

which were then explored further by gaining opinions from multiple stakeholders to assess the importance of various treatment attributes and levels.

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with multiple patient and clinician stakeholders to identify and rank treatment attributes and levels. These were conducted with UK patient representatives (n=14) and clinical experts (n=6).

The key themes identified in the interviews included ‘the effect of gene therapy on daily life’ and the importance of ‘informed decision making’. The following attributes about haemophilia treatments in general were ranked by clinician and patient stakeholders as the top 5 most important: ‘effect on factor level’ (79 points), ‘uncertainty regarding long-term risks’ (57 points), ‘impact on daily life’ (41 points), ‘frequency of monitoring’ (33 points), and ‘impact on ability to participate in physical activity’ (29 points). The top 5 categories ranked as the most important when considering gene therapy as a treatment option included: ‘benefits’ (135 points), ‘quality of life’ (86 points), ‘risks’ (85 points), ‘administration’ (61 points) and ‘follow up’ (33 points).

- Phase 2 –Based on findings from Phase 1, five attributes and levels were further defined and validated for inclusion in the DCE, and the final DCE scenarios were produced. Variables for inclusion in the participant questionnaire were also refined. An orthogonal DCE design was chosen to define the number of scenarios to include in the study and the sample size requirements were adjusted dependent on the number of selected attributes and levels. This phase is now complete.

During this phase, five key attributes with different levels were developed and validated. These were reviewed by experts in health literacy from Northwestern University and 2 UK patient advocates with haemophilia, to ensure they were appropriate, and understandable from an English health literacy perspective. Following further adaptation of the attributes and levels during subsequent detailed consultations with expert stakeholders (a UK haemophilia consultant and a UK psychologist), a further 2 UK patient advocates also provided feedback. This led to further revision of the levels’ wording to improve understanding and reduce cognitive burden.

The final five attributes selected for the DCE were:

- Therapeutic option
- Treatment effectiveness
- Safety concerns
- Hospital attendances and self-management
- Role limitations

During this process a decision was made to include an additional exploratory analysis in the DCE design, using levels from one domain of the Short-Form-Six-Dimension version 2 (SF-6Dv2) utility instrument (alongside collection of the full SF-6Dv2 responses within the questionnaire). The aim was to utilise an innovative technique to demonstrate quality adjusted life year (QALY) equivalence. This approach uses a

	<p>domain from a utility instrument (SF-6Dv2) in place of one of the DCE attributes: ‘Role limitations’. The calculation element of this approach will use partial values between levels in the utility domain included in the DCE, in combination with utility tariffs (in this case the SF-6Dv2), to estimate the utility value associated with each level. In combination with the baseline utility, collected in the administration of the full SF-6Dv2 during the participant questionnaire, the utility gain achieved by a participant moving from worst to best in the DCE attribute levels can then be estimated.</p> <p>A pilot study using the full study online platform (educational video, questionnaire and DCE) was then conducted with seven patient advocates in the UK, who provided feedback, including their estimates of the various levels of risk presented within the ‘Safety concerns’ attribute. Adjustments to the study, including further improving the wording of levels in the DCE, were made to meet any changes required.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Phase 3 – study conduct: this involves delivering the study (including the DCE) in an electronic format, administered to PWH in the UK online, to elicit participant preferences. This phase launched on 11th December 2020 and study participation is ongoing. Participants who meet the inclusion criteria (see Study Population) enter into the study via a secure web-link, read a participant information document and complete an online informed consent form. <p>Participants first watch a short, online educational video about gene therapy, which was developed by MindBytes, in collaboration with the University of Leuven. This video was validated by the University of Leuven in consultation with 3 Belgian consultant haematologists who specialise in haemophilia, and 10 Belgian PWH. It also received input from Pfizer UK Medical Affairs and Health and Value colleagues and a Pfizer Global Medical Affairs colleague. It was reviewed by health literacy experts from Northwestern University and 2 UK patient advocates with haemophilia from an English health literacy perspective. This video will not collect any data and is for informing participants only.</p> <p>After watching the video, participants then complete an online questionnaire to answer baseline demographic, clinical, knowledge, comprehension and satisfaction questions. Data from variables in this questionnaire will be used to examine predictors of preferences for the various treatment attributes. Data are also gathered on quality of life (utilities), captured by participants completing the SF-6Dv2. Participants then complete the DCE, where for each of 14 hypothetical scenario sets they will choose 1 of 2 scenarios, deciding between levels presented for each of the 5 attributes listed above. Descriptives for demographic, clinical and quality of life information will be performed, and analyses as detailed in ‘Statistical Methods’ will be conducted to estimate the value of each of the treatment attributes and levels, and to identify groups of PWH who may value treatment attributes differently.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Phase 4 –Interpretation of the findings from the qualitative and DCE study phases and dissemination of this information. The results of this study will be comprehensively summarised in a final report. The findings will be published as research papers in peer-reviewed journals and presented as abstracts and posters at suitable conferences.
Study Population	Participants must meet all of the following inclusion criteria to be eligible for inclusion in the study:

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Aged 18 years or older 2. Able to read written English 3. Live in the United Kingdom 4. Diagnosed with moderate or severe haemophilia A or B 5. Have provided informed consent to participate in the study <p>A minimum total of 120 people with moderate or severe hemophilia (A and B) in the UK will be recruited, aiming for recruitment of a minimum of 25 participants with haemophilia B to ensure adequate representation of this subgroup. This calculation was based on the ratio of people with haemophilia A to haemophilia B in the UK population, as per the UK National Haemophilia Database Bleeding Disorder Statistics for 2018-2019, produced by the UK Haemophilia Centre Doctors' Organisation (UKHCDO). In addition, following the completion of the phases for the development of possible attributes and levels (Phases 1 and 2), including the pilot study, a further exploration of minimum sample size requirements was performed based on sample size calculations and the number of attributes and levels.</p>
Exposure & Outcome	<p>Exposure: This is a non-interventional study, consisting of participants watching a brief educational video on gene therapy in haemophilia, then completing a questionnaire to elicit demographic, clinical, knowledge and comprehension information, and the SF-6Dv2 to determine quality of life scores, then completing a DCE to elicit patient preferences for gene therapy in haemophilia.</p> <p>Outcomes: The variables captured in the questionnaire, the SF-6Dv2 scores, and the participant responses in the DCE scenarios, are the data for analysis. The main endpoints of interest are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preference weights for all attribute levels in the DCE • Conditional relative importance of each attribute • Marginal rates of substitution among attributes
Study Setting	<p>All data from the study are being collected through an electronic questionnaire and DCE completed online by PWH in the UK. Recruitment of these participants is being managed by the UK Haemophilia Society. The online link to the study platform is being distributed to PWH in the UK by the Haemophilia Society, who contact their members via email and also on social media platforms (invitation-only Facebook and WhatsApp groups operated by the Haemophilia Society).</p>
Statistical Methods	<p>All data processing and analyses will be performed with STATA 16.0 statistical software (STAT Corp., College Station, TX). The baseline demographics collected in this study will be summarised, alongside any clinical and quality of life information collected in the participant questionnaire and SF-6Dv2. The results captured from the DCE will be used to generate a coefficient for each level of each attribute in the experimental design.</p>

	<p>Conditional logit will be used to analyse responses from the DCE as it allows us to relate the probability of choice among two or more alternatives to the characteristics of the attribute levels defining those alternatives. The result of this analysis generates a preference weight which represents the relative contribution of the attribute level to the utility that respondents assign to an alternative.</p> <p>The mixed logit model, or random-parameters logit (RPL) model, is a logit model for which the parameters are assumed to vary from one individual to another. It is therefore a model that takes the heterogeneity of the population into account. The RPL model relates respondents' treatment choices to the attribute levels of each treatment profile in the choice questions. The RPL model mitigates potential estimation bias in the mean preference weight estimates because of unobserved preference heterogeneity among respondents by estimating a distribution around each mean preference parameter and accounts for the fact that each respondent made multiple treatment choices over a series (panel) of choice questions. In the RPL models, preference heterogeneity was assumed to follow a continuous normal distribution.</p> <p>Subgroup analyses will be conducted using the RPL model in order to examine systematic differences in preferences between subgroups. Subgroup analyses may or may not provide much information about the correlation between preference heterogeneity and observed characteristics of the respondents. To further explore preference heterogeneity and differences in preferences among respondents with different characteristics, latent class modeling can be considered. Here the researcher assumes a discrete, rather than a continuous, mixing distribution to describe preference heterogeneity among respondents in the sample.</p> <p>A cluster analysis, a form of latent class analysis, will be carried out to identify groups of PWH who may value treatment attributes differently. Due to limitations with the conditional logit model such as scale and preference heterogeneity, other exploratory modelling methods may be explored that overcome these possible limitations. However, this will not be the prespecified primary outcome due to relatively small sample size and ability to converge.</p>		
Results	PREFER Research Questions	How was it addressed in this preference study	What was found
	To investigate how patient preferences can be used in decision making	Conduct of a DCE with planned analysis of the relative contributions of different attributes and levels to patient decision making in PWH	TBC
	To understand how patient preference studies can be conducted in rare diseases	Conduct of a DCE in PWH; haemophilia is a rare disease	TBC

	<p>To investigate differences in preferences with varying levels of disease severity (11d)</p>	<p>Planned analyses for patient preferences elicited in the DCE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subgroup analyses using the RPL model to examine systematic differences in preferences between subgroups (including haemophilia severity subgroups). • Cluster analysis to identify groups of PWH (e.g. with differing severities) who may value treatment attributes differently. • Latent class modelling to explore preference heterogeneity and differences in preferences among respondents with different characteristics (including severity). 	<p>TBC</p>
	<p>To investigate how to ensure patient preference information from preference studies is applicable/tailored to HTA/payer decision making (15b)</p>	<p>Planned presentation of patient preference study design at the Pfizer haemophilia B gene therapy NICE scientific advice meeting (11 February 2021). This will aim to elicit feedback from NICE on how patient preference studies will be valued by NICE and how results of patient preference studies such as this one should be included in, and appraised by, future HTA or other approval submissions.</p>	<p>TBC</p>
<p>Conclusions</p>	<p>To date, results are only available from the initial, qualitative phases of the study (Phases 1 and 2). In Phase 1, the key themes identified in the interviews included ‘the effect of gene therapy on daily life’ and the importance of ‘informed decision making’. The following attributes about haemophilia treatments in general were ranked by clinician and patient stakeholders as the top 5 most important: ‘effect on factor level’ (79 points), ‘uncertainty regarding long-term risks’ (57 points), ‘impact on daily life’ (41 points), ‘frequency of monitoring’ (33 points), and ‘impact on ability to participate in physical activity’ (29 points). The top 5 categories ranked as the most important when considering gene therapy as a treatment option included: ‘benefits’ (135 points), ‘quality of life’ (86 points), ‘risks’ (85 points), ‘administration’ (61 points) and ‘follow up’ (33 points). These results demonstrate that treatment benefits, treatment risks and quality-of-life impact are important factors to inform treatment selection and decision-making when patients are considering whether to proceed with gene therapy for haemophilia. These factors may also be useful to highlight to regulators and HTA</p>		

	<p>bodies (such as NICE) in future discussions and submissions about gene therapy for PWH, particularly in the UK.</p> <p>Phases 1 and 2 were essential in defining the five attributes to be used in the DCE (Therapeutic option; Treatment effectiveness; Safety concerns; Hospital attendances and self-management; Role limitations).</p>
<p>Limitations</p>	<p>As choice data in DCEs are collected by using health profiles based on hypothetical alternatives, some possible attribute-level combinations could be implausible or illogical. Participants may have difficulty evaluating such illogical combinations, which could increase the potential for hypothetical bias, unobserved, heterogeneous interpretations by participants; or lower response efficiency. The design approach of the DCE was therefore amended to specify combinations that should not appear in the DCE. In addition, poorly defined attributes and levels would provide biased and potentially meaningless interpretations of choices and preferences. As such, the various study phases tried to ensure the reliability and validity of choosing attributes for the DCE.</p> <p>There are many methodological approaches that can be implemented to inform the choice of DCE attributes, including literature reviews, expert opinion, meta-ethnography and use of previous studies. Qualitative research involving stakeholder semi-structured interviews in Phase 1 was important in the development of relevant attributes for the DCE. However, qualitative research tends to be explorative and expansive, whereas with designing DCE a reductive process is necessary. As such, it was not possible to include all potential attributes which could be relevant, but rather infer which attributes are preferred.</p> <p>A DCE is a stated preference study and some patients may find the task cognitively challenging. The number of possible attributes presented was limited to include only the most important attributes for PWH based on the targeted literature review and the qualitative research undertaken. The DCE was also reviewed by 2 different sets of patient advocates to gain feedback during the attribute/level refinement process. The initial attributes and levels arising from the qualitative study phase were validated in an independent manner by Northwestern University, who also consulted 2 patient advocates in the UK to ensure that the health literacy of these attributes and levels was appropriate for participants. Following further adaptation of the attributes and levels during subsequent detailed consultations with further expert stakeholders (a UK haemophilia consultant and a UK psychologist), a further 2 patient advocates in the UK provided feedback. This led to revision of the levels' wording to improve understanding and reduce cognitive burden. The DCE was then tested via a pilot study in a group of 7 patient advocates in the UK. Feedback from the pilot study was used to improve further the wording of some of the attribute levels, before finally launching the study in the UK PWH population in December 2020.</p> <p>This study includes an exploratory analysis, aiming to infer QALY equivalence with the use of a domain from the SF-6Dv2 included as one of the attributes within the DCE (Role limitations). This exploratory analysis has, to date, not been reported in a peer reviewed publication, nor in a published HTA, therefore the validity</p>

	<p>of this approach is still to be established. This limitation does not impact the interpretation of attribute 5 (role limitations) within the overall DCE study.</p>
<p>Potential Use of Results in MPLC Decision-Making</p>	<p>Patients and/or caregivers: For PWH and their caregivers, who may be faced with the decision on whether or not to choose gene therapy for their haemophilia, this study provides a means for preferences to be elicited and key attributes that determine choice to be explored.</p> <p>Industry: The results of this study will be helpful to industry in informing development decisions about gene therapy for haemophilia. The preferences expressed in the DCE may provide guidance on what benefit-risk trade-offs may be acceptable, and to whom, including what kind of patient-related factors (demographic or clinical) may influence these decisions.</p> <p>The DCE results may contribute to regulatory guidance on use of preferences or specific methods in decision making. In addition, these results may help to inform reviews of gene therapy in HTA or other submissions, for approval or reimbursement decisions.</p>
<p>Transferability</p>	<p>TBC once results of the DCE (main study) are available. This study is being conducted in PWH in the UK, so this must be appreciated when considering transferability of results to PWH in other countries that have different healthcare systems and treatment options.</p>

Diabetes

Therapeutic Area	Diabetes
Core Case Study, Academic Case Study, Industry Case Study	Academic Case Study
Academic Lead, Industry Lead, Methods Lead, Clinical Lead	<u>Academic Lead</u> : Ardine de Wit, Jorien Veldwijk, Esther de Bekker-Grob <u>Methods Lead</u> : Jorien Veldwijk, Esther de Bekker-Grob
Title of the Study	Preferences of diabetic patients for different glucose monitoring devices
Background/ Study Rationale	Recent developments in glucose monitoring devices have led to preference-sensitive decisions where patients have a large variety of choices in regard to function, features, cost, and other factors to consider when choosing which glucose monitor is best for them. This study aims to determine the preferences and trade-offs of diabetes patients when selecting a device for monitoring their glucose, and to determine whether these outcomes differ by type of preference elicitation method used, the kind of educational tool they are presented with, and if patient characteristics or experiences can explain preference heterogeneity
MPLC Decision-making	<u>Main stakeholder</u> : The primary stakeholders for this type of study are industry and HTA. Industry stakeholders can use this information to target development of new devices that meet market needs. HTA stakeholders can use this information to better calculate predicted uptake rates.
	<u>MPLC decision point of interest</u> : Pre-discovery and Post approval
Clinical Research Questions	<u>Clinical research question #1</u> : Which attributes of blood glucose monitoring devices do patients consider when deciding on their preferred device? What is the relative importance of these different attributes in choosing which devices to use?
	<u>Clinical research question #2</u> : What are the minimum required benefits needed to justify increased costs?

<p>Methodological Research Questions</p>	<p><u>Methodological research question #1(2d)</u>: How do preference values vary between different preference assessment methods with varying complexity when applied to the same population sample?</p> <p><u>Methodological research question #2 (7d)</u>: Are preferences for devices different (i.e. overall preference accuracy and variability of preferences) when patients are educated regarding blood glucose monitoring using enhanced educational material vs traditional textual information?</p> <p><u>Methodological research question #4 (11a)</u>: Can preference heterogeneity be explained based on type of diabetes, geographic or socioeconomic factors (e.g. country of origin, age, sex)?</p>
<p>Study Design</p>	<p><u>Qualitative pilot</u>: In step 1, a scoping literature review was conducted in PubMed to identify relevant attributes of glucose-monitoring devices and develop an interview guide. In step 2, semi-structured interviews were conducted with Type 1 and 2 diabetes patients (n=19), clinicians (n=5), patient organization representatives (n=2), and pharmaceutical industry representatives involved in glucose monitoring device development (n=4). The resulting list of 12 attributes identified in steps 1 and 2 were rated and reduced according to relevance, completeness, non-redundancy, operationality, and preferential independency to a final list of 7 attributes with 2 to 4 levels each.</p> <p><u>Quantitative pilot</u>: The draft questionnaire containing the enhanced educational material, Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE), and Swing Weighting (SW) tasks along with all other questions was pre-tested during six ‘think-aloud’ tests, checking for comprehensibility and clarity. The survey was then revised and pilot tested in a sample of 99 participants in order to retrieve priors to inform the design of the final DCE. After the pilot test of the DCE, the DCE design with three alternatives per choice task was substituted by a “best-best” or a so-called ‘dual response’ DCE.</p> <p><u>Main study</u>: Participants were randomized to receive either text or enhanced educational material prior to completing the survey. In addition, the order in which the participants completed the DCE or SW was also randomized after the information was presented.</p> <p><u>Educational materials</u>: A script was developed based on input from clinicians, patient representatives, and a review of educational materials provided to patients through clinics and patient organization websites. The script consisted of two parts: general information about diabetes and diabetes self-management using glucose monitoring, and information about the attributes used in the DCE and SW tasks. The need for general information on diabetes and diabetes self-management was based on interviews with clinical experts who highlighted this need and research showing that many diabetes patients were never properly educated about the basics of diabetes self-management, the</p>

	<p>importance of keeping glucose under control, and how to use glucose monitoring to help this. An animated version of the text was created with a voiceover to account for possible low levels of health literacy.</p> <p><u>DCE</u>: Bayesian D-efficient designed DCE was developed, consisting of three blocks of 12 choice tasks. Each choice task was presented in a dual response design in which participants were first asked to choose between two alternative devices and then to choose between the alternative chosen or a status quo opt-out. Each alternative was described using seven attributes across 22 levels. Participants were given two ‘warm-up’ DCE choice-tasks before the main exercise in order to ensure comprehension. The attributes used in the DCE were precision compared to fingerprick, average number of fingerpricks per day, effort to check, probability of getting skin irritation or redness, monthly costs, glucose information, and alarms.</p> <p><u>SW</u>: The SW task consisted of a ranking exercise in which participants rank, in regards to importance, the “swing” of an attribute if it were to change from its worst to its best. This was followed by a direct rating of the swings in which participants had to rate the swings on a scale from 0 to 100 with the highest rated swing automatically receiving 100 points.</p> <p><u>Psychosocial constructs</u>: Three psychosocial constructs were assessed. These were subjective numeracy (SNS-3), health literacy (Chew’s Health Literacy screening questions), and patient activation (Patient Activation Measure; PAM). In addition to this, diabetes self-management was assessed (Diabetes Self-Management Questionnaire-Revised, DSMQ-R)</p>
Study Population	Adults (age ≥ 18 years), self-reporting diagnosis diabetes with no restriction on type of diabetes, who reside in the Netherlands (N=459 panel respondents) and Poland (N=522 panel respondents); able to give informed consent; able to verbally communicate by themselves; able to read, speak, and understand Dutch or Polish; have access to a computer with internet connection
Exposure & Outcome	<p><u>DCE</u>: The results of the DCE were used to generate utility values for the individual attribute levels, relative attribute importance values, attribute rankings, willingness-to-pay estimates, and expected uptake rates.</p> <p><u>SW</u>: The results of the swing weighting were used to generate attribute importance rankings and relative attribute importance values.</p>
Study Setting	Online survey completed by patient panels respondents in the Netherlands and Poland

<p>Statistical Methods</p>	<p>Effects coded mixed-logit models were used to analyze the DCE outcomes. SW was analyzed using relative preference scores and rank order centroid analysis. Comparison of self-reported feedback from participants indicating how easy the methods were to understand and answer.</p>		
<p>Results</p>	<p>PREFER Clinical and Methodological Research Questions</p>	<p>How was it addressed in this preference study</p>	<p>What was found</p>
<p>Clinical Questions:</p>			
<p>Which attributes of blood glucose monitoring devices patients consider when deciding on their preferred device?</p>		<p>DCE: Effects coded mixed-logit models SW: Rank Order Centroid and proportional weighting</p>	<p>For both Dutch and Polish patients, the most important attributes were monthly costs and precision compared to fingerpricking.</p>
<p>What are the minimum required benefits needed to justify increased costs?</p>		<p>DCE: Effects coded mixed-logit models</p>	<p>Polish respondents were more likely than Dutch respondents to choose an optimal device, a Freestyle Libre proxy device, or cheaper Freestyle Libre proxy compared to a standard finger-prick. Polish respondents also had a higher willingness to pay than Dutch respondents for a device. Dutch respondents were more willing to pay for improvements in effort to check and reducing the number of fingerpicks a device may require.</p>
<p>Methodological Questions:</p>			

	<p>How do preference values vary between different preference assessment methods with varying complexity when applied to the same population sample?</p>	<p>Comparison of attribute proportional importance weights; Self-reported feedback from participants indicating how easy the method was to understand and answer; comparison of attribute (relative) importance</p>	<p>Similar rankings were identified in the DCE and SW for the most important attributes. The variance in proportional weight distributions were higher when assessed using DCE outcomes than when assessed using SW outcomes. The DCE had a 14.9-fold difference between the most and least important attribute, while the SW had a 1.4-fold difference and all attributes receiving 12-17% of the proportional weight. The DCE was reported by participants to be both easier to understand and to complete, compared to the SW.</p>
	<p>Are preferences for devices different (i.e. overall preference accuracy and variability of preferences) when patients are educated regarding blood glucose monitoring using an enhanced educational tool vs traditional textual information?</p>	<p>Comparison of effects coded mixed-logit model outcomes; comparison of time to complete survey</p>	<p>No systematic difference was found between the two educational tool types in either each country. Slight differences were found in parameter estimates, but these differences did not result in different outcomes after applying the estimates to expected uptake rates. The amount of time that participants spent in the choice tasks indicates that</p>

			educational material was not highly utilized.
	Can preference heterogeneity be explained based on type of diabetes, geographic, or socioeconomic factors (e.g. country of origin, age, sex)?	Latent Class Analysis	Significant statistical differences were found between the two countries in regards to parameter estimates. These differences did not result in different outcomes after applying the estimates to expected uptake rates. Latent Class assignment for at least one class was significantly associated with the general demographics of country of origin, age, and education level, and level of health literacy and numeracy. In addition, class assignment for at least one class was significantly associated with the medical history characteristics of years with diabetes, current insulin and device usage, and current spending on care. This heterogeneity was associated with differences in WTP and uptake rate prediction estimates.
Conclusions	Similar patterns of preferences were seen within the two countries in regards to the most important attributes when choosing a glucose monitoring device. The primary difference was how the finger-prick was valued. Data regarding attribute ranking was similar for both DCEs and SW methods. DCEs were considered easier to use by participants and resulted in more detailed information for stakeholders to use. Patients showed similar preferences between countries,		

	<p>but differences in willingness-to-pay and uptake rates estimates were found. The limited time spent in the educational tools raises questions about whether the educational tools were actually utilized or only seen as a hurdle to get to the actual choice tasks.</p>
<p>Limitations</p>	<p>The data is limited to preferences reported by panel participants. Results of a preference study done in participants recruited via clinical partners may result in different findings. This study was unable to recruit via these channels due to COVID-19 restrictions in research participation by clinical partners as a response to increased demand associated with COVID-19. Differences between the two countries regarding healthcare availability and healthcare costs may make the patient groups incomparable. Panel respondents self-reported as having diabetes with no way to verify this. Additionally, the educational levels of the two countries were different as the Polish population was more highly educated than the Dutch population.</p>
<p>Potential Use of Results in MPLC Decision-Making (Optional)</p>	
<p>Transferability (Optional)</p>	<p>The transferability of the clinical findings is likely limited. Differences in relative importance for the non-cost attributes between the two countries and the significant associations between preferences and patient characteristics make it difficult to apply these findings outside of the countries and samples in which the studies were conducted. The similarity of findings relative to the comparison of techniques and the limited attendance to the educational tools in this experienced patient population are likely transferable outside of the current case study.</p>

Haemophilia

Therapeutic Area	Hemophilia and gene therapy
Core Case Study, Academic Case Study, Industry Case Study	Academic case study
Academic Lead, Industry Lead, Methods Lead, Clinical Lead	<u>Academic Lead</u> : Isabelle Huys (KU Leuven) & Eline van Overbeeke
Title of the Study	Patient preferences to Assess Value IN Gene therapies (PAVING)
Background/ Study Rationale	Recently, gene therapy for the treatment of hemophilia has been developed. Clinical trial results are promising. However, multiple challenges remain. These challenges mainly relate to the fact that it is currently still unknown whether the therapeutic effect of gene therapy will be maintained throughout the full lifespan of patients, and what side effects may occur in the long run.
MPLC Decision-making	<u>Main stakeholder (industry, regulatory, HTA)</u> : HTA <u>MPLC decision point of interest</u> : HTA/reimbursement
Clinical Research Questions	Identify attributes of gene therapy and standard of care that are important to patients
	Understand trade-offs that patients make when choosing between gene therapy and standard of care
Methodological Research Questions	Question 1.11/5b: What approach can be used to determine which patient preference method to use for a given circumstance?
	2.31/11d To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with Disease experience or severity
	2.14/4a2 Which presentation formats respondents prefer (displays, video, descriptions, etc.)
	3.12/15b How to ensure patient preference information from preference studies are applicable/tailored to HTA/payer decision making
Study Design	Interviews and threshold technique
	<u>Educational materials</u> : Educational tool on gene therapy
	<u>Psychosocial constructs</u> : Chew Health literacy screening questions
Study Population	Patients diagnosed with moderate or severe hemophilia A or B, 18 years or older, and living in Belgium
Exposure & Outcome	Minimum acceptable benefit

Study Setting	Hemophilia reference centers and patient organizations from April-May 2020		
Statistical Methods	Interval regression and plotting of thresholds		
Results	PREFER Clinical and Methodological Research Questions	How was it addressed in this preference study	What was found
	Clinical Questions:		
	Identify attributes of gene therapy and standard of care that are important to patients	Interviews including: open questions, ranking exercise and case questions	Top 5: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual bleeding rate • Factor level • Uncertainty long-term risks • Impact on daily life • Probability that prophylaxis can be stopped
	Understand trade-offs that patients make when choosing between gene therapy and standard of care	Threshold technique using 4 attributes in 2 labelled profiles (gene therapy vs. prophylactic factor replacement therapy)	Included attributes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual bleeding rate (ABR) • Chance to stop prophylaxis (STOP) • Time that side effects have been studied (TIME) • Quality of life (QOL)
	Methodological Questions:		
	Question 1.11/5b: What approach can be used to determine which patient preference method to use for a given circumstance?	Method selection was based on assessment of methods according to different selection criteria	In the context of gene therapy for a rare disease the threshold technique was found most suitable.
	2.31/11d To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with Disease experience or severity	Disease severity (severe vs. moderate hemophilia) is included in the covariate-adjusted regression model to assess the effect of disease severity on preferences	Severity of disease (mod vs sev) had no influence on preferences.

	<p>2.14/4a2 Which presentation formats respondents prefer (displays, video, descriptions, etc.)</p>	<p>In interviews written text was discussed with the patient and preferences were investigated on how patients wanted the information to be formulated and presented. An educational tool was then designed for the quantitative phase and was further refined with patients.</p>	<p>Patients wanted information on gene therapy to be communicated using animations. The educational tool that was used in the survey effectively educated participants on gene therapy and increased acceptance of gene therapy (i.e. the more time participants spent on the tool, the less benefit they required to accept gene therapy).</p>
	<p>3.12/15b How to ensure patient preference information from preference studies are applicable/tailored to HTA/payer decision making</p>	<p>The PAVING study was supported by an advisory board that included, amongst others, HTA and payer decision makers. The advisory board provided feedback on study design to ensure their design and quality needs were met.</p>	<p>Advisory board reached a consensus on attribute classes to explore: benefits (including clinical endpoints and QoL), risks, and administration + to exclude: costs.</p>
<p>Conclusions</p>	<p>Interviews showed that most hemophilia patients have a positive attitude toward gene therapy and that besides efficacy, safety and the related uncertainties, also impact on daily life is important to patients. Results from the threshold technique survey proved that education may facilitate patients' acceptance of novel treatments. Moreover, preference heterogeneity for novel treatments was confirmed in this study.</p>		
<p>Strengths & limitations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The sample was representative of the Belgian hemophilia population • Available therapies for hemophilia other than gene therapy and prophylactic factor replacement therapy were not considered 		
<p>Potential Use of Results in MPLC Decision-Making</p>	<p>The identified patient-relevant attributes may be used by regulators, health technology assessment bodies and payers in their evaluation of gene therapies for hemophilia. Moreover, they may inform clinical trial design, pay-for-performance schemes and real-world evidence studies. The quantitative results may be used to inform value propositions and budget impact analysis. In gene therapy decision-making, preference heterogeneity and the impact of patient education on acceptance should be considered.</p>		

Transferability	Transferability to other countries may be limited.
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Multiple Myeloma

Therapeutic Area	Multiple Myeloma (MM)
Core Case Study, Academic Study, Industry Study	Academic Study
Academic Lead, Industry Lead, Methods Lead, Clinical Lead	Academic Leads: Rosanne Janssens (KU Leuven), Prof. Isabelle Huys (KU Leuven) Clinical Leads: Prof. Dr. Michel Delforge (KU Leuven/UZ Leuven), Dr. Elena Cabezudo (Hospital de Sant Joan Despí Moisés Broggi. Consorci Sanitari Integral/ICO-Hospitalet), Dr. Raija Silvennoinen (Helsinki University Hospital), Dr. Daniel Coriu (Clinica de Hematologie), Prof. Dr. Fredrik Hellem Schjesvold Methods Lead: Prof. Martina Vandebroek (KU Leuven) Patients' Organizations Leads: Ananda Plate (MPE), Jayne Galinsky (MPE), Tamika Lang (MPE), Ana Vallejo (MPE), Kate Morgan (MPE), Chris De Ronne (CMP Flanders)
Title of the Study	Patient Preferences for Multiple Myeloma Treatments
Background/ Study Rationale	Treatments for Multiple Myeloma (MM) in development and use today are associated with a range of different characteristics and related uncertainties, such as novel side-effects, long-term effects, and efficacy outcomes. This raises questions about what matters most to MM patients. Understanding preferences among MM patients is especially valuable in decision-making surrounding MM treatments, where uncertainty exists about the key factors that drive MM patients when considering MM treatments. Furthermore, decisions surrounding MM treatment can be labelled 'preference sensitive': i) it is unknown which attributes (e.g. benefits, risks) of MM and MM medical products are most important to patients, ii) multiple MM treatment options exist and there is no option that is clearly superior for all patients, iii) there is a need to understand MM patients' acceptability for uncertainty regarding MM treatments, and iv) there is a need to understand MM patient preference heterogeneity, i.e., how attribute weights are influenced by relevant patient characteristics such as clinical and demographic characteristics.
MPLC Decision-making	Main stakeholder (industry, regulatory, HTA): industry, regulatory, HTA MPLC decision-points of interest: This study may inform industry, regulatory and HTA decision-making regarding MM treatments on patient-relevant treatment attributes. More specifically, results from this study could be used by pharmaceutical companies to allocate resources towards developing drugs that not only improve life expectancy but as well target quality-of-life related symptoms and side-effects, such as mobility problems, pain, neurotoxicity's, and thinking problems. Second, results from the MM study may support regulators and HTA bodies in requiring drug developers to augment evidence about how MM treatments perform against these patient-relevant quality-of-life related side-effects and symptoms. Third, the MM study findings can be used by regulators and HTA bodies during benefit-risk assessment and relative effectiveness

	<p>assessments respectively to increase their understanding of whether the MM treatment being evaluated address the unmet needs, symptoms, side-effects and uncertainties most important to patients. Finally, the MM study may inform healthcare providers about which (long-term) MM treatment-related uncertainties, symptoms, and side-effects should be systematically and clearly communicated to patients during individual treatment decision-making in clinical practice.</p>
<p>Clinical Research Questions</p>	<p>The overall aim of this study was to gain insights into the preferences of MM patients regarding different characteristics of MM treatments. The study consisted of two sequential phases (sub-studies), whereby the qualitative study informed the attributes, the levels and their descriptions, further investigated in the quantitative study (see “Study Design”). The research questions of these phases were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Qualitative study:</i> Which characteristics MM patients find most important, and hence should be included as attributes and levels in a subsequent quantitative preference survey among MM patients? • <i>Quantitative study:</i> What is the quantified importance (“weight”) of relevant MM treatment attributes? How are MM patients’ preferences influenced by their characteristics such as demographic characteristics, treatment experience, and disease stage?
<p>Methodological Research Questions</p>	<p>The methodological research questions of the quantitative study were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do Swing Weighting (SW) and Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) compare in the elicitation of MM patient preferences? • What was MM participants’ experience with the survey, and the DCE and SW preference elicitation questions?
<p>Study Design</p>	<p>The study consisted of two sequential phases (sub-studies), whereby the qualitative study informed the attributes, levels and their descriptions included in the quantitative study. The design of in these phases was:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Qualitative study:</i> This phase involved three stages: i) a scoping literature review, to identify the characteristics associated with MM treatments in development and use today, ii) discussions with a heterogeneous sample of MM patients (n=24) in Belgium, Finland, Romania, and Spain using Nominal Group Technique, to understand which of these are most important and should be included as attributes and levels in the quantitative study; iii) a combined quantitative and qualitative thematic analysis involving multi-stakeholder discussions with patients and clinicians, to refine the language and explanation of the attributes, levels and their descriptions for inclusion in the quantitative study. • <i>Quantitative study:</i> An online survey was widely spread among the MM patient population across Europe to quantify the relative value of the attributes and the trade-offs they are willing to make between hypothetical MM treatments or MM treatment effects. The survey used both Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) and Swing Weighting (SW) to quantify patients’ preferences towards the same attributes. The DCE questions asked respondents to make hypothetical choices between two

hypothetical MM treatments, which differed in how they performed on the different attributes identified in the qualitative study. SW directly captured individual patient preferences for each attribute. Instead of choosing between full treatment scenarios, respondents of the SW experiment were asked for their preferences for moving from the worst to the best levels (swings) on each attribute. Two treatment alternatives per DCE choice task were included. In view of the complexity of the choice tasks, no opt-out option was included; as it could have triggered participants to select this option when the choice task is difficult and thereby give limited information on treatment preferences. For the same reason, more than two alternatives would have made the choice task too difficult. Regarding the levels, two levels were included for each of the attributes in the DCE and SW questions, since the methodological aim of this study was to compare DCE with SW and the SW questions only elicit preferences for the swing from the worst to the best level (= two levels), and a linear preference for all attributes was expected.

The online survey contained the following components:

1. Introduction
2. Information form
3. Informed consent form
4. SW questions*
5. Patients' self-reported comprehension and evaluation of the SW questions*
6. DCE questions*
7. Patients' self-reported comprehension and evaluation of the DCE questions*
8. Background questions (clinical and demographic characteristics, quality of life of patients (EQ-5D questionnaire))
9. Patients' evaluation of the complete survey including a question asking their preference for DCE vs SW questions

*Half of the participants were randomly assigned to receive the DCE (+ comprehension and evaluation questions) questions first and afterwards the SW (+ comprehension and evaluation questions), whereas the other half first performed SW (+ comprehension and evaluation questions) and afterwards the DCE (+ comprehension and evaluation questions) questions. Sawtooth Software¹ was used construct the DCE tasks and implement the online survey. Participants could complete the survey with a laptop, a smartphone or a tablet. The survey was developed in English and translated to the native languages of the participants (Dutch, English, Finnish, French, German, Romanian and Spanish) by a professional translation company. These translations were then checked for accuracy and lay-language by team members who are native speakers of the language used in the survey

¹ <https://www.sawtoothsoftware.com/>

	<p>and/or patient organization members part of the study team or their members. The survey was reviewed and/or pre-tested by MM patients (5 in total across countries) to obtain patients’ feedback on the overall survey and more specifically: i) their understanding of the questions (including the attributes and their descriptions), ii) their understanding of the purpose of the elicitation tasks and usefulness of the explanation preceding the elicitation tasks, iii) whether the survey was not too lengthy and iii) any other feedback.</p> <p><i>Educational materials:</i> The DWE and SW questions were preceded by a succinct section of written information that explained the attributes, the levels, how the DCE and SW questions worked and what the purpose of the elicitation questions was. In view of the length of the preference survey, no educational video was included in addition. To assess the usefulness of the educational component, LIKERT questions asking for patients’ evaluation and comprehension were included following both the SW questions and the DCE questions.</p> <p><i>Psychosocial constructs:</i> Health literacy (the patient’s ability to read, understand, and use healthcare information appropriately) of participants was assessed via the inclusion of the validated 3-item questionnaire, Chew’s Set of Briefing Screening Questions (Chew et al., 2004)</p>
Study Population	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Qualitative study:</i> Haematologists recruited 24 MM patients across 4 countries (Belgium, Finland, Spain, and Romania), who were diverse in terms of treatment experience, and disease stage. During recruitment, the haematologists kept in mind that goal of this study was to ensure that the attributes identified were not directed only to patients with a specific treatment exposure, disease history or country of origin; but rather towards all patients along the MM spectrum. During sampling, haematologists used the following inclusion criteria: i) patients diagnosed with symptomatic MM; ii) patients ability to understand the language to be used in the discussion and iii) patients ability to participate in the discussion. Six MM patients were included in each of the four countries: Belgium, Finland, Romania and Spain. These countries were included to account for potential differences in patient characteristics and, as mentioned above, and ensure the identified attributes are not geared only to patients with a specific treatment or disease history. A much larger number above 6 patients would delay the phased process of the NGT discussion which aims to reach consensus in a short time span (up to 2 hours). Saturation, the point when “no new information or themes are observed in the data”, was used to define when data collection could stop. Following qualitative data collection in the four countries, it appeared that the same themes of treatment attributes were observed across different countries. Hence, it was decided that no additional data was needed to inform the attributes. • <i>Quantitative study:</i> The online survey was widely disseminated through the European MM patient population (n=393) via patient organizations and haematologists, from January 21st 2021 to April 21st 2021. A combination of different recruitment approaches (see below) was used to include a

	<p>large and heterogeneous sample of participants. This was done to ensure the study results reflected preferences across MM patients with varying backgrounds and enable the investigation of preference heterogeneity (i.e. how the attribute weights are influenced by relevant patient characteristics such as clinical and demographic characteristics such as treatment experience, disease stage, age, and country). Recruitment occurred via email (sent by clinical partners and E-newsletters by patient organizations), social media (websites of the patient organizations, Twitter, Facebook, and LinkedIn, disseminated by patient organizations and academic study partners), telephone (by clinical partners and patient organizations), and face-to-face, during the hospital visit (by clinical partners). To increase inclusiveness towards MM patients, likely not well versed in technology, participants were encouraged to contact the researchers and ask for technical support. Native speaking study contributors were available to assist with enquiries in a participant’s specific language. Further, haematologists focused on recruitment of elderly participants.</p> <p>Regarding sample size, it was sought to maximize sample size to facilitate an in-depth analysis to evaluate preference heterogeneity. Sawtooths’ test design option was used to test the efficiency of the design prior to survey launch. This test simulates random respondent answers and reports the standard errors (using a logit model) and thereby allows to estimate the precision of the DCE design for a given (anticipated) number of participants. This test revealed that for 350 respondents, standard errors for each of the levels were equivalent and maximally .03, hence below the recommended .05. Therefore, while recruitment sought to include as many participants as possible, a minimal number of 350 participants was aimed for, which was also deemed feasible according to the patient organizations and haematologists who performed the recruitment.</p>
<p>Exposure & Outcome</p>	<p>The results from this study are extremely suitable to be presented to and discussed with patients, and drug decision-makers, including drug developers, regulatory and HTA stakeholders – who might benefit from using the results from this study to inform their decisions. Therefore, substantial (ongoing) efforts focus on spreading the study results as broadly as possible and towards all healthcare stakeholders, and this via oral and poster presentations of the results on conferences (e.g., DIA GLOBAL, DIA EUROPE, ISPOR EUROPE, ..) as well as via scientific publications already published and currently being written. Patient organizations are involved in the development of each of these publications and conference presentations, thereby helping to disseminate the results and enabling them to utilize the findings in advocacy efforts.</p>
<p>Study Setting</p>	<p>The invitation, information sheet, informed consent and link to the online survey was disseminated via social media, telephone, hospital visit, face-to-face and e-mail. Persons recruiting were the study contributors, hematologists, patient organizations, hematology associations and relevant scientific associations.</p>
<p>Statistical Methods</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Qualitative study:</i> ANOVA and Fischer exact tests were performed to investigate statistically significant differences in between groups of participants between countries. In addition, a combined

quantitative descriptive analysis of patients' rankings and iterative qualitative thematic analysis on the discussion transcripts was used to determine the attributes. Participants' self-reported characteristics (including health literacy) were analysed descriptively using Microsoft Excel. The average grades for the characteristics were calculated per country to derive rank orders and averages at country level. To obtain a final rank of the themes capturing the characteristics, the averages for each of the treatment characteristics pertaining to a theme was calculated by combining the averages obtained in the four countries.

- *Quantitative study:* The type of statistical analysis depended on what was required for meeting the research objectives, and the type of data collected:
 - To quantify the importance (“weight”) of patient-relevant treatment attributes
 - SW questions: Attribute weights and rank orders were derived both from the SW point allocation questions and the SW ranking question. For the point allocation questions, the attribute weights were firstly calculated and then the attributes were organized from most to least important according to their weights. To derive the attribute weights from the SW allocation questions, participants' individual average weights were normalized using their individual average weight for survival, which was kept constant between all SW point allocation questions. For the ranking question, the attribute weights were firstly calculated and then the attributes were organized from most to least important according to their weights. To derive the attribute weights from the SW ranking question, the sum of participants' individual ranks for each of the attributes was calculated and divided by the total sum of allocated ranks for all attributes. The attributes were then organized from most to least important according to the attribute weights.
 - DCE questions: Conditional Logit (CL), Latent Class (LC) and Mixed Logit (ML) models were fitted to the data to determine the rank order and relative weight of each attribute. First, CL was used to reveal whether the attribute concepts significantly affected respondent choices. LC and ML models were used as final models; LC because it enabled the identification of segments of respondents with similar preferences and allowed the investigation of differences in respondents' characteristics between these classes (see 'Preference heterogeneity'). ML, estimated using Hierarchical Bayes (HB), was used in addition because of its effectiveness for the estimation of individual parameters when participants are given only a few choices. The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) were used to select the final LC model. For the ML model, percentage certainty and root likelihood (RLH) were used to describe goodness of fit. Based on

	<p>the relative importance and 95% confidence interval (CI) obtained for each attribute, the attributes were ranked most to least important.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To investigate how the attribute weights are influenced by patient characteristics (preference heterogeneity): Two types of analyses were conducted to investigate the presence of statistically significant preference heterogeneity. The first type of analysis used the latent classes of the best fitting LC model to group participants and assess statistical differences between these classes on patients’ characteristics, namely demographics (age, gender, country), experienced side-effects, symptoms and previous treatment experience. Particularly, the class assignments (the categorical assignment of each respondent to their most likely class) of the best fitting LC model was used as a grouping variable. Cross tabulations, chi-square analyses and multivariate analyses of variance (MANOVAs) were then performed against these patients’ characteristics, depending on the variable type (categorical vs. continuous). The second type of analysis investigated statistical differences between participants’ individual attribute weights, derived via the DCE and SW questions, according to the same variables using cross-tabulations, chi-square analyses and MANOVA - again depending on the variable (categorical vs. continuous). ○ To compare SW and DCE: The rank order and relative attribute weights obtained through SW vs. DCE choice tasks were compared qualitatively. To explore reasons for differences between DCE and SW results, participants’ evaluation of the DCE and SW questions were investigated (see ‘Participants’ self-reported comprehension and evaluation of survey’).. ○ To assess participants’ self-reported comprehension and overall evaluation of the SW and DCE questions: Descriptive analyses were used to evaluate patients’ responses to the closed survey questions that elicited participant feedback on their comprehension of the survey, on the DCE and SW questions and an evaluation of the overall survey. Conversely, qualitative analysis was used to evaluate participants’ answers to the open questions such as respondents’ evaluation and comprehension of the SW and DCE choice tasks, and overall survey impression. 		
Results	PREFER Research Questions	How was it addressed in this preference study	What was found
	<i>Qualitative study:</i> Which characteristics do MM patients find most important and hence should be included as	<i>See ‘study design’:</i> Three stages: i) a scoping literature review, to identify the characteristics associated with MM treatments in development and use today, ii)	This qualitative study revealed the concerns and key treatment aspects that are most important for MM patients, and hence were included as attributes in the subsequent preference survey. In particular, MM patients voiced significant expectations and hopes that treatments extend their lives and reduce their cancer signs and symptoms. Participants were afraid of

	<p>attributes and levels in the quantitative study?</p>	<p>discussions with a heterogeneous sample of MM patients (n=24) in Belgium, Finland, Romania, and Spain using Nominal Group Technique, to understand which of these are most important and should be included in the quantitative study; iii) a combined quantitative and qualitative thematic analysis involving multi-stakeholder discussions with patients and clinicians, to refine the language and explanation of the attributes, levels and their descriptions for inclusion in the quantitative study.</p>	<p>serious side-effects that are life-threatening and could cause permanent organ damage. Bone fractures and debilitating neuropathic effects (such as chronic tingling in their feet) were highlighted as major issues reducing patients' independence and mobility. Patients also discussed the adverse impact of the following symptoms and side-effects on their daily activities: difficulties to think clearly and concentrate, increased susceptibility to infections, reduced energy, pain, emotional problems, and vision problems. MM patients were concerned with uncertainties regarding the durability of positive treatment outcomes, as well as the cause, severity, and duration of their symptoms and side-effects. MM patients feared short-term positive treatment responses complicated by permanent, severe side-effects and symptoms. Participants emphasized that their individual opinions and preferences were shaped by their previous treatment and disease experience; participants more frequently raised those symptoms and side-effects they had previously experienced. Based on the qualitative thematic and quantitative analysis, the following eleven attributes were identified: i) additional life expectancy in years; ii) risk of life-threatening side-effects; iii) expected treatment response; iv) duration and severity of nerve or bone problems affecting movement; v) duration and severity of thinking problems; vi) duration and severity of increased susceptibility to infections; vii) duration and severity of reduced energy; viii) duration and severity of pain; ix) duration and severity of emotional problems; x) duration and severity of eating- and digestive problems; xi) duration and severity of vision problems. These attributes were included in the subsequent preference survey that aims to determine the relative value of these attributes and the trade-offs MM patients are prepared to make</p>
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	<p><i>Quantitative study:</i> What is the quantified importance (“weight”) of relevant MM treatment attributes? How are MM patients’ preferences influenced by their characteristics such as demographic characteristics, treatment experience, and disease stage?</p>	<p>See ‘<i>study design</i>’: An online survey among the MM patient population that quantifies the relative value of these attributes and the trade-offs they are willing to make between hypothetical MM treatments or MM treatment outcomes. The survey used Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) and Swing Weighting (SW) to quantify patients’ preferences towards the attributes (see ‘<i>study design</i>’).</p>	<p>between these attributes. The DCE survey uses a partial-profile design, showing four attributes of the eleven attributes in each DCE question.</p> <p>The quantitative phase revealed that, among the attributes, the average MM participant considered life expectancy most important. Furthermore, on average, mobility problems, pain, thinking problems and treatment response scored among the five most important attributes. Conversely, reduced energy, emotional problems, increased susceptibility to infections, and eating and digestive problems scored among the six least important attributes. Importantly however, the ranges of participants’ individual attribute weights derived from both the DCE and SW tasks revealed substantial and significant preference heterogeneity; patients’ preferences were highly influenced by participants’ age, disease experience, severity, and status, and their past experiences with side-effects, symptoms, and treatment outcomes. Furthermore, statistical analyses investigating preference heterogeneity revealed that MM participants with intermediary treatment experience placed relatively more value on quality of life-related attributes such as pain, mobility and thinking problems than on life expectancy and treatment response. No statistical differences were revealed between attribute values of patients participating from different countries, indicating that participants living in different European countries had no significantly different preferences. MM participants highlighted: i) the difficulty of trading-off between improvements in life expectancy vs. quality of life, and between improvements in their physical vs. mental health; ii) the psychological burden of dealing with uncertainties regarding long-term treatment outcomes, side-effects and symptom burden, and iii) their need for more psychological, mental, and social support.</p>
<p>Conclusions</p>	<p>Results from this study argue in favor of MM drug development that not only focuses on extending patients’ lives but also on addressing those symptoms and side-effects that significantly impact MM patients’ quality of life. This study underscores a need for transparent communication towards MM patients about the uncertainties regarding the long-term efficacy and safety of MM treatments. Finally, this study may help understand which quality of life-related treatment outcomes are most important to MM patients and therefore should be considered for systematic incorporation in MM drug development and evaluation. From a methodological viewpoint, this scope of research provides a foundation for an evidence-based approach</p>		

	<p>on the appropriate conduct of both qualitative and quantitative patient preference studies, for which currently no evidence-based guidelines exist that encompass the design, conduct, and analysis of patient preference studies. Therefore, this research provides crucial information to support drug development, regulatory, and reimbursement decisions by integrating the true patient perspective, preferences, and insights into impacts on patient quality of life. This research is unique in that it integrates patient and patient organization feedback into all aspects of study design and data collection, therefore, lending to be a more robust and patient-focused scope of research.</p>
<p>Limitations</p>	<p><i>Qualitative study:</i> The impact of the COVID-19 on this research is especially relevant since this study consisted of qualitative discussions with MM patients, who have a higher susceptibility to infections. Conducting this study during COVID-19 required flexibility from both participants and study team. For the online and telephone discussions, it is likely that participants, who were not comfortable with online discussions or telephone (e.g. elder participants), were less likely to participate. The study team tried to be as inclusive as possible during recruitment, by offering both face-to-face and online discussions, according to the preferences of the participants and the local social distancing and hospital guidelines. Further, technical support for participants was given throughout the entire study. A steps-wise guideline explaining the practicalities of the discussion beforehand, and ensuring there was an opportunity, before the session for participants to test whether they could participate in the discussion. Still, the median age of diagnosis of patients included in this study was 55, which is 11 years younger than the median age reported by Kazandijan² in 2016 and 14 years younger than the average age of diagnosis reported by ASCO³ in 2020. Further regarding generalizability, it is important to note that the purpose of this study was not to make statements about a population larger than the included sample. Rather, it aimed to gain in-depth insight into the opinions of patients participating in the discussions including which attributes are important to them and why.</p> <p><i>Quantitative study:</i> As for the limitations of the quantitative study, it is important to reflect on differences between the relative importance's obtained via the SW point allocation, SW ranking, and DCE questions. In an ideal scenario, the inclusion of these different question types would have allowed to perform head-to-head comparisons for each of the attributes. However, the appropriateness of this comparison was limited by the existence of differences in question formats, lack of application of a statistical model to estimate the SW attribute values combined with a large preference heterogeneity. For this study, due to limitations in the SW question formats (difficulty</p>

² <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5283695/#R2>

³ <https://www.cancer.net/cancer-types/multiple-myeloma/risk-factors#:~:text=Myeloma%20occurs%20most%20commonly%20in,occur%20in%20people%20under%2040>

	<p>in patient understanding), as well as in the SW analysis (lack of statistical modelling), the DCE results rather than the SW result should be considered for understanding relative attribute importance's and rank order. Importantly, this experience should not hamper researchers in considering the use of SW in their surveys. Rather, this experience argues that SW as applied in this study should be improved by simplifying it according to patients' feedback, and by applying an external statistical model such as the Dirichlet distribution, which has been proposed by Tervonen et al., for modeling population preferences. Further, the survey revealed the difficulty patients experienced with evaluating hypothetical scenarios with attributes that patients sometimes or often have not had experienced. This underscores the importance of using patient-relevant lay-language that accurately and precisely describes the attributes and their impact. Following patients' feedback, in order for patients to make informed choices in the preference study (but likely as well in daily clinical practice), the disease and treatment effects described towards patients should outline the impact of these effects on patients' life expectancy and quality of life, as well as any uncertainties related to these. Clear attribute descriptions are especially important for patients not having experienced these, and when the attributes concern rare (severe) disease or treatment effects. Finally, findings from this study may be limited by the fact that, while, in the context of the PREFER project, the MM preference study design was presented to regulatory and HTA stakeholders at various occasions, they were never formally asked to reflect on the study aim, design and results as outlined above. Therefore, a subsequent necessary step would be the organization of appropriate discussions fora such as the ongoing qualification procedure of a framework for patient preference studies proposed by the PREFER consortium, being evaluated by EMA and EUnetHTA. This would enable understanding their views on the study design, and the MM preference study findings revealed and described in the present study.</p>
<p>Potential Use of Results in MPLC Decision-Making</p>	<p>There are multiple opportunities by which the MM study can inform decision-making across the medicinal product life cycle, and in particular:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The allocation of resources by pharmaceutical companies to drugs that not only improve life expectancy but as well target health related quality-of-life (HRQoL) symptoms and side-effects, such as mobility problems, pain, neurotoxicity's, and thinking problems; • The formulation of evidence requirements by regulators and HTA bodies in early scientific advice, parallel consultations and post-marketing; requiring pharmaceutical companies to augment evidence about how MM treatments perform against these patient-relevant quality-of-life related side-effects and symptoms via HRQoL instruments and patient reported outcome (PRO) measures, both during clinical development (prior to marketing authorization) as well as following marketing authorization (in the form of real world evidence); • The selection (by drug developers) and assessment (by regulators and HTA bodies) of these patient-relevant clinical outcomes and trial endpoints;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory benefit-risk assessment and marketing authorization, by improving regulators’ understanding of whether the MM treatment being evaluated answers an unmet medical need and by helping them in identifying key (un-)favorable effects and uncertainties for inclusion in the effects table; • Relative effectiveness assessments by HTA bodies, by informing their assessment on whether the MM treatment being evaluated address the unmet needs and treatment outcomes most important to patients; • The identification of areas where a need exists for increased transparency and communication about treatments between patients, regulators, healthcare providers and payers and; • Individual treatment decision-making in clinical practice between healthcare providers and patients to inform healthcare providers about which (long-term) MM treatment-related uncertainties, symptoms, and side-effects should be systematically and clearly communicated to patients.
Transferability	<p>The identified attributes and levels of the MM study were perceived relevant to different types of patients in terms demographics (age, gender and country) treatment and disease experience (years since diagnosis, experienced side-effects and symptoms, worst side-effects and symptoms experienced, current and past MM treatment experience), health literacy, and quality of life, and this was facilitated by an inclusive recruitment approach where different types of patients were included via the combination of several recruitment channels (physicians, patient organizations, social media). An inclusive recruitment approach hence increased the transferability of the identified patient relevant attributes and levels which followed from our research objectives; namely to understand unmet needs and treatment outcomes of importance to MM patients with varying treatment exposure, disease history, age, or country of origin; and in addition, to investigate preference heterogeneity. To increase the transferability of the study findings (i.e., the identified attributes of the qualitative phase and the conclusions regarding relative attribute weights and preference heterogeneity in the quantitative phase) towards different types of MM patients, ‘member checking’ was applied, meaning that ‘external’ MM patients, i.e., those meeting the target patient group but who were not included in the samples of both the qualitative and quantitative study, were asked to check the findings to assess how key findings matched with their own experience. Such external MM patients were furthermore asked to review and provide input on a lay version of the study results, and this included an evaluation of whether the conclusions regarding the identified prioritized attributes from the qualitative phase, and the average attribute ranks from the quantitative phase, made sense from other patients’ point of views and whether the conclusions regarding preference heterogeneity were in line with what they would expect, based on their own disease experience and treatment preferences, or what they saw among other patients. The preference study findings were also externally validated by evaluating them against with patients’ actual, i.e., non-hypothetical treatment choices and preferences; i.e., a validation of the study findings with</p>

patients to assess how the key conclusions regarding the prioritized attributes and conclusions regarding attribute weights and preference heterogeneity, resonate with what matters most to patients and assessing how they compare with how patients make treatment choices in real life. In addition to validating the results with patients matching the patient population included in the study, hematologists and study nurses also reflected on the study results (i.e., the identified attributes of the qualitative phase and the conclusions regarding relative attribute weights and preference heterogeneity in the quantitative phase) with what they see among other patients that match the patient population included in the study, i.e., as seen in clinical practice.

The inclusion of a large and heterogeneous sample in the quantitative phase enabled to reveal which variables significantly affected the value patients placed on attributes and hence such variables should be viewed as limiting the transferability of the relative attribute weights across MM patients that differ with respect to those variables. The quantitative survey phase also revealed those variables that did not significantly impact preferences, and hence could allow for transferring the results between patients differing with respect to these variables. Specifically, variables significantly affecting individual relative attribute weights were: i) participants' number of current and past drug therapies, ii) the type(s) of therapy(-ies) they had taken, iii) whether they had experienced the side-effects and symptoms they were asked to evaluate in the preference questions, and iv) age. Depending on treatment experience, patients valued quality of life more than life expectancy or *vice versa*; whereas patient at the beginning and end of treatments found life expectancy more important than any other attribute, the patients in the middle of their treatment found attributes related to life quality (such as pain, mobility and thinking problems) more important. The quantitative MM survey also found statistical differences ($p < .05$) between participants' attribute weights depending on their age. Furthermore, through the open MM survey questions and in the qualitative MM patient discussions, patients themselves indicated that their answers to preference questions were highly affected by their disease severity (mild MM vs. severe MM), disease stage (early diagnosis or more progressed) and status, past experiences with side-effects, symptoms, and treatment outcomes. Several participants indicated also that it was difficult to evaluate attributes (side-effects, symptoms) they had not yet experienced.

In view of preference heterogeneity with respect to these variables, average attribute weights should likely be best presented per patient groups that are similar regarding these variables (participants' number of current and past drug therapies, the type(s) of therapy(-ies) they had taken, whether they had experienced the side-effects and symptoms they were asked to evaluate in the preference questions, and age) to understand how much average attribute values differ between these groups. Conversely, no statistical differences were revealed between individual attribute weights depending on participants' country, region, health literacy, their professional and financial status, whether they had children, or were in a relationship.

Hence a lack of preference heterogeneity with respect to these variables could allow for transferring the average attribute weights between patients varying with respect to these variables. Of note, while country as such was not found to significantly impact patients' preferences, the inclusion of additional countries likely indirectly helped to increase the transferability of the study results because it allowed to include additional patients and increase heterogeneity in the patient sample with respect to disease and treatment experience. It could finally be hypothesized that different (additional) attributes could be revealed when new medical products are in development and/or enter the market; since then, patients may experience such novel treatment effects and uncertainties, and find these new side-effects and uncertainties important; such that these attributes should be included in subsequent preference surveys.

Rheumatoid arthritis

Therapeutic Area	Rheumatoid arthritis, second-line treatment
Core Case Study, Academic Case Study, Industry Case Study	Academic case study
Academic Lead, Industry Lead, Methods Lead, Clinical Lead	<u>Academic Lead</u> : Ulrik Kihlbom, Karin Schölin Bywall <u>Methods Lead</u> : Jorien Veldwijk
Title of the Study	Assessing patients with rheumatoid arthritis preferences for second-line treatment using an educational tool: a discrete choice experiment in a regulatory decision-making context in Sweden
Background/ Study Rationale	Patient preference studies needs to be tailored to the regulatory context in order to provide useful information in an understandable and accurate form to inform regulatory marketing authorisation decisions. The inclusion of patient preferences in regulatory marketing authorisation decisions is currently hindered by the lack in guidance on when and how to assess patient preferences and how to use this information. More best practice patient preference studies are critically needed to support the development of such guidance.
MPLC Decision-making	<u>Main stakeholder (industry, regulatory, HTA)</u> : This study may support decisions in the regulatory marketing authorisation process by providing information on what is most important for patients with rheumatoid arthritis and compares the effect of an educational tool to traditional written information on the outcomes of a DCE study. <u>MPLC decision point of interest</u> : Patient preference information assessed by this study may provide important additional information in decisions relating to a renewal of an existing drug or for an approval of a new drug (submission and validation, scientific opinion, commission decision).
Clinical Research Questions	<p>To elicit RA patient preferences (including risk-benefit trade-offs and relative importance of attributes) for biologics and JAK-inhibitors when changing treatment.</p> <p>To what extent do patient characteristics explain preference heterogeneity amongst patients with rheumatoid arthritis in Sweden?</p> <p>To estimate minimum acceptable benefit of patients with rheumatoid arthritis for changing to biologics and JAK-inhibitors</p>
Methodological Research Questions	<p>To what extent does the application of an educational tool (vs standard written information) influence patient preferences as well as the outcomes of a discrete choice experiment? 1.16 (7d)</p> <p>To what extent do psychological constructs (health literacy and numeracy) provide insight regarding the accuracy and consistency of patient preferences? 1.19, (10b1)</p>

<p>Study Design</p>	<p>The attributes for the discrete choice experiment were developed via a scoping literature overview, validation meetings with experts, and focus groups with patients. A preliminary list of attributes and attribute levels drafted from the scoping literature overview was revised based on feedback from the validation meetings and the focus group meetings. Seven attributes were included in the discrete choice experiment: mode of administration, frequency of use, probability of mild short-term side effects, probability of side effects changing appearance, probability of psychological side effects, probability of severe side effects, and treatment effectiveness.</p> <p><u>Educational materials:</u> Respondents received the same training content in one of two forms: either as a written (plain) text or as an educational tool that used graphics, pictograms, icon arrays, voice-over, and click-on functions. The educational tool was developed and illustrated with assistance from MindBytes, (http://www.mindbytes.be).</p> <p><u>Psychosocial constructs:</u> Measures of health literacy, and subjective numeracy were included.</p>																								
<p>Study Population</p>	<p>The following inclusion criteria were used: diagnosis of rheumatoid arthritis; between 18–80 years old; able to understand and answer the questions; and able to read and understand Swedish without aid.</p>																								
<p>Exposure & Outcome</p>	<p>The survey started with information about rheumatoid arthritis and available treatment options before entering the DCE. The last section of the survey consisted of demographic and disease-related questions, health literacy, and numeracy. The DCE had an attribute-based D-efficient experimental design. Each respondent answered 15 hypothetical choice questions characterised by varying attribute levels. Participants were asked to choose their preferred treatment from two alternatives. Each attribute was described by three levels based on current clinical knowledge of existing biologics and JAK inhibitors (table 1).</p> <p>Table 1. Attributes and levels</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="521 1045 1740 1453"> <thead> <tr> <th>Attribute</th> <th>Level 1</th> <th>Level 2</th> <th>Level 3</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Route of administration</td> <td>Tablet</td> <td>Injection</td> <td>Drip</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Frequency of use</td> <td>Daily</td> <td>Weekly</td> <td>Monthly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Probability of mild short-term side effects (nausea, vomiting or headache)</td> <td>Common, 1 in 10</td> <td>Uncommon 1 in 100</td> <td>Rare 1 in 1000</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Probability of side effects changing appearance (hair loss, weight changes or skin rash)</td> <td>Common, 1 in 10</td> <td>Uncommon 1 in 100</td> <td>Rare 1 in 1000</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Probability of psychological side effects</td> <td>Common, 1 in 10</td> <td>Uncommon 1 in 100</td> <td>Rare 1 in 1000</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Attribute	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Route of administration	Tablet	Injection	Drip	Frequency of use	Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Probability of mild short-term side effects (nausea, vomiting or headache)	Common, 1 in 10	Uncommon 1 in 100	Rare 1 in 1000	Probability of side effects changing appearance (hair loss, weight changes or skin rash)	Common, 1 in 10	Uncommon 1 in 100	Rare 1 in 1000	Probability of psychological side effects	Common, 1 in 10	Uncommon 1 in 100	Rare 1 in 1000
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	<p>(anxiety, mood changes, depression or sleep disturbance)</p> <table border="0"> <tr> <td data-bbox="546 331 913 499">Probability of severe side effects that requires hospitalisation such as severe infections or allergic reactions</td> <td data-bbox="925 331 1160 363">Common, 1 in 10</td> <td data-bbox="1182 331 1400 395">Uncommon 1 in 100</td> <td data-bbox="1473 331 1668 363">Rare 1 in 1000</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="546 507 913 675">Effectiveness (the ability to decrease inflammation and swelling of the joints, also pain and other symptoms)</td> <td data-bbox="925 507 1160 842">30 % improvement So out of 100 persons taking the treatment, 30 will get enough improvement, the rest will get a small or no improvement</td> <td data-bbox="1182 507 1400 770">50 % improvement So out of 100 persons taking the treatment, 50 will get enough improvement, the rest will get a small or no improvement</td> <td data-bbox="1473 507 1668 770">70 % improvement So out of 100 persons taking the treatment, 70 will get enough improvement, the rest will get a small or no improvement</td> </tr> </table> <hr/> <p>Outcomes calculated were: attribute level estimates, relative importance scores, minimum acceptable benefit, preference heterogeneity.</p>	Probability of severe side effects that requires hospitalisation such as severe infections or allergic reactions	Common, 1 in 10	Uncommon 1 in 100	Rare 1 in 1000	Effectiveness (the ability to decrease inflammation and swelling of the joints, also pain and other symptoms)	30 % improvement So out of 100 persons taking the treatment, 30 will get enough improvement, the rest will get a small or no improvement	50 % improvement So out of 100 persons taking the treatment, 50 will get enough improvement, the rest will get a small or no improvement	70 % improvement So out of 100 persons taking the treatment, 70 will get enough improvement, the rest will get a small or no improvement
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Study Setting	Recruitment of patients with rheumatoid arthritis started in November 2018 and ended in October 2019. In total, 673 respondents were included in the analysis. Patients were recruited via three sources: a research panel (n=162) (dynata.com); the Swedish Rheumatism Association (n=228); and the rheumatology clinic at Uppsala University Hospital, Sweden (n=283).								
Statistical Methods	<p>Assessing preferences: Latent class analysis models were used for the analysis of the DCE data. Such models account for the multilevel structure of the data (i.e., every respondent answered multiple choice questions) and allow for the investigation of preference heterogeneity.</p> <p>Minimum acceptable benefit was estimated as the difference between the preference weights (parameters) for two levels of an attribute divided by the preference weight.</p> <p>Assessing impact of educational tool: Random parameter logit models were used to estimate attribute levels and heterogeneity in preferences</p> <p>Relative importance scores were calculated based on results of a random parameter logit model separately for the plain text and the educational tool. The difference between the highest and lowest estimates of the attribute level was calculated for each attribute.</p>								

Results	PREFER Clinical and Methodological Research Questions	How was it addressed in this preference study	What was found
Clinical Questions:			
	To elicit RA patient preferences (including risk-benefit trade-offs and relative importance of attributes) for biologics and JAK-inhibitors when changing treatment.	Attribute level estimates Relative importance of the attributes Trade-offs between benefits and risks	Latent class analysis revealed three preference patterns. When choosing treatment, the respondents found either effectiveness of treatment (34%), mode of administration (28%), or probability of severe side effects to be most important (38%).
	To what extent do patient characteristics explain preference heterogeneity amongst patients with rheumatoid arthritis in Sweden?	Latent class analysis > class assignment model	Disease duration and experience in mild side effects influenced preferences.
	To estimate minimum acceptable benefit of patients with rheumatoid arthritis for changing to biologics and JAK-inhibitors	Minimum acceptable benefit	Patients noting effectiveness as most important were more willing than other patients to accept higher risks of side effects
Methodological Questions:			
	To what extent does the application of an educational tool (vs standard written information) influence patient preferences as well as the outcomes of a	Compared educational tool to written information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scale & choice consistency • Dominant decision making. • Time of completion • Drop-out • Perceived understanding and difficulty of the questionnaire 	The outcome of the scale test showed that the estimates, but not the error variances, were significantly different across the two data sets.

	<p>discrete choice experiment?</p>	<p>Compared the outcomes of a DCE when using either an educational tool or standard written information</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attribute levels estimates • Relative importance of the attributes • Trade-offs between benefits and risks 	<p>There were no differences in reported difficulty or the time taken to answer the DCE questions between the study arms. Respondents informed by the educational tool placed relatively more importance on treatment side effects, and respondents receiving the plain text placed relatively more importance on the treatment effectiveness and the administration methods.</p>
	<p>To what extent do psychological constructs (health literacy and numeracy) provide insight regarding the accuracy and consistency of patient preferences?</p>	<p>The effect of health literacy and numeracy on preferences and understanding of the survey instrument will be assessed by comparing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responses to warm up questions • Scale & choice consistency Survey internal validity checks • Perceived understanding and difficulty of the questionnaire 	<p>There were no identified effects of health literacy and numeracy.</p>
<p>Conclusions</p>	<p>On average, respondents found either effectiveness, severe side effects, or mode of administration as the most important attribute. Patients noting effectiveness as most important were more willing than other patients to accept higher risks of side effects. Compared to the respondents receiving the plain text, the respondents receiving the educational tool placed relatively more importance on the side effects. However, uncertainty remains regarding how educational tools influence preferences and the results of a DCE. Further research is needed to provide guidance on how and when to use educational tools to inform and elicit patients' preferences.</p>		
<p>Limitations</p>	<p>A limitation of this study relates to the use of three different recruitment strategies. This was a pragmatic choice to facilitate achievement of a sufficient number of respondents in order to power the statistical analysis. However, a sensitivity analysis did not identify any systematic differences in respondents' preferences for the attribute levels depending on recruitment source.</p>		

<p>Potential Use of Results in MPLC Decision-Making</p>	<p>Information on the relative importance of treatment characteristics and preference, heterogeneity within patients' preferences and the minimum acceptable benefit may provide essential information in the regulatory scientific evaluation.</p>
<p>Transferability</p>	<p>The results might also be relevant to industry, health technology assessment bodies/reimbursement agencies, physicians and patients. Patient preferences may support the pharmaceutical industry by revealing the minimum acceptable benefit required in order to accept an increase in the chance of getting a certain side effect. Information that might support the pharmaceutical company's application to a marketing authorisation. These results have the potential to inform the decision on whether to reimburse an authorised medical product by presenting the most important treatment characteristics. This research provides an overview of differences in treatment preferences. Such results may lead to more accurate and acceptable marketing authorisation decisions that may improve the progression of disease management. This research may be transferable to physicians in patient discussion when considering benefits and risks of treatment alternatives.</p>

Conclusion

This report provides a summary of the additional case studies conducted by academia and industry as part of PREFER. All case studies wrote a full report on their methods, results, and conclusions, following a standard template. Assessment of the results of all studies was done within the individual case study report as well as in Tasks 3.9 and Task 3.10. Separate reports for the latter two reports are available as well. Experiences from the 8 additional case studies, as well as from the 3 core case studies, have been used to draft recommendations in PREFER work package 4.

Appendix 1: Review checklist

PREFER reviewer checklist

Information for reviewers: these review sheets will be made available to PREFER members. At the end of the project, aggregated lessons learned may be compiled and posted publicly on the PREFER website. This summary may contain de-identified feedback from reviewers. The aim of a PREFER review at this stage is to review if the case study, according to the new more detailed information in the protocol compared to the synopsis:

- Addresses prioritized research questions from PREFER
- Is considered feasible given previously approved budget and timelines
- Will add to PREFER recommendations

Furthermore, a high level scientific review is expected (no detailed scientific content review required).

Case study title	Reviewer name; date of review
PREFER project case study:	

Reviewer overall recommendations [for review of protocol]
<input type="checkbox"/> Case study protocol is approved without comments and can be send for IRB or <input type="checkbox"/> Case study protocol approved with minor comments, after editing given the provided comments the protocol can be send for IRB or <input type="checkbox"/> Case study protocol should be re-submitted to the PREFER review committee

Criteria for review of case study protocol	Y / I / N [Yes/Inadequately/No]	Reviewer comments (obligatory to complete when assigning 'inadequately' or 'no' for a given criterion)
The rationale of the case study is clearly described		
The primary and secondary clinical and methodological objectives address prioritized PREFER research questions		
The methods selected to address the primary and secondary clinical and methodological objectives for the study are aligned with those recommended from WP2, are adequately described in the protocol (high-level overview), NB: A separate statistical analysis plan will describe the detailed descriptive and modeling strategy].		
The analytical approaches for the primary and secondary clinical and methodological objectives are suitable to address the objectives as described (i.e., can provide valid answers). NB: A separate statistical analysis plan will describe the detailed descriptive and modeling strategy].		
The study population proposed for the case study is suitable to provide valid answers to the proposed research questions		
Inclusion and exclusion criteria are clearly described and sample size is justified		
Procedures on consent and participant withdrawal are clearly described, also it is described how this will be communicated to the study participants		
Data management is appropriately described at high level <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Details about which personal and/or sensitive data will be collected are described and submitted to IMI before the collection of data ▪ Copies of approvals for the collection of personal data by the Institutional Data Protection Officer / National Data Protection authority are submitted to IMI before the collection of data 		

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ PREFER obtains written approval for the technical procedures that will be used for data protection for the project from each institution where data will be collected. These procedures must demonstrate compliance of the data protection processes with the present European legal frame. A copy of this approval will be submitted to IMI before the collection of data. ▪ Detail of the level of de-identification of the different source of data and how protection of personal data is assured and approved by an ethical board and provided to IMI before the use of data ▪ If personal and sensitive data will be processed and transferred between non-EU and EU countries, relevant authorizations are provided to IMI before the use of any personal/sensitive data not publicly available ▪ Detailed information on dissemination of results in case of rare diseases is approved by the Ethical Committee and a copy of this approval is submitted to IMI before dissemination ▪ Details of any planned exchanged or transfer of samples and personal data with non-EU countries together with appropriate authorizations are provided before transfer / exchange 		
<p>Results of this case study will contribute to the PREFER recommendations to be written in WP4</p>		
<p>Proposed study is considered feasible given the provided budget, team composition and timelines</p>		
<p>There is a publication and dissemination strategy listing proposed scientific and lay publications</p>		

Any additional comments from reviewer that are not covered by criteria above:

Appendix 2: Deliverable template (final study report template)

DX.YY Deliverable Title

115966 – PREFER Patient Preferences in Benefit-Risk Assessments during the Drug Life Cycle

[WPX – WP Title]

Lead contributor	Name (Org number – Org Name)
	Email
Other contributors	[Please include all organisations involved in this deliverable] Name (Org number – Org Name)
	[Please include all organisations involved in this deliverable] Name (Org number – Org Name)
	[Please include all organisations involved in this deliverable] Name (Org number – Org Name)
Due date	dd Mmm YYYY
Delivery date	dd Mmm YYYY
Deliverable type	R, DEM, DEC, OTHER ⁴
Dissemination level	PU, CO, CL ⁵

Description of Work	Version	Date
	VX.X	dd Mmm YYYY

⁴ Use one of the following codes:

R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

⁵ Please choose the appropriate reference and delete the rest:

PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web;
CO = Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement;
CI = Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.

1. Introduction

1.1 Clinical background

1.2 Preference sensitive situation, related stakeholder(s) and decision-point

(See Task 2.3 for decision point descriptions: see <https://service.projectplace.com/pp/pp.cgi/r225250925>)

Please describe:

- **Which decision, by whom** (industry and/or regulator and/or HTA body) is expected to be informed by the results from the patient preference study, and how the preference data will be used (preference data in isolation, or preference data together with clinical & other data) to inform the decision
- **The type of scenario(s) prompting the preference study** (scenario about what matters / how much does it matter / acceptability of trade-offs / acceptability of uncertainty)
- **Whose preferences are of interest**

1.3 Clinical research questions

List all clinical research questions as reported in PREFER approved synopsis and protocol that are investigated in the final study (elaborate on RQ that are no longer part of the case study due to external events such as COVID-19)

1.4 Methodological research questions

List all methodological research questions as reported in PREFER approved synopsis and protocol that are investigated in the final study (elaborate on RQ that are no longer part of the case stud due to external events such as COVID-19)

(please link these research questions (RQs) back to the question numbers for Task 2.8:
<https://service.projectplace.com/pp/pp.cgi/r225288238>)

1.5 Study team

Please indicate who is head of research (principle investigator(s)) in which institute(s).

2. Methods

2.1 Qualitative phase

2.1.1 Strategy for participant identification and recruitment

- *Inclusion criteria*
- *Exclusion criteria*
- *Recruitment strategy (Including recruitment source (e.g. panel, clinical site, etc))*
- *Any changes to the planned approach that did not warrant separate ethics committee approvals (please describe deviations from original protocol as submitted to ethics reviews).*

2.1.2 Ethical consideration

- *Describe patient Information and consent procedure*
- *Describe patient withdrawal options*
- *Describe Institutional Review Board (IRB)/Independent Ethics Committee (IEC) that reviewed and approved the protocol (state if the ethics committee has approved any approach to communicating final results to patients and patient organizations)*

2.1.3 Methodology description

- *Describe methodology and all relevant steps undertaken, whenever available based on evidence-based guidelines. Include a description of approach to pilot testing and number of subjects for pilot testing*
- *When executing the study in multiple countries: approach to translation of patient materials*
- *Any changes to the planned approach that might not have warranted separate ethics committee approvals*

2.1.4 Statistical considerations and data analysis

- *Describe endpoints per RQ (both clinical and methodological)*
- *Statistical analysis for the analysis of each endpoint*
- *Anticipated sub-group analysis*
- *Sample size calculation*
- *Any changes to the planned analyses: why and how?*

2.2 Quantitative phase

2.2.1 Participant identification and recruitment (as described in the protocol)

- *Inclusion criteria*
- *Exclusion criteria*
- *Recruitment strategy (Including recruitment source (e.g. panel, clinical site, etc))*
- *Any changes to the planned approach that might not have warranted separate ethics committee approvals*

2.2.2 Ethical consideration

- *Describe patient Information and consent procedure*
- *Describe patient withdrawal options*
- *Describe Institutional Review Board (IRB)/Independent Ethics Committee (IEC) that reviewed and approved the protocol (state if the ethics committee has approved any approach to communicating final results to patients and patient organizations)*

2.2.3 Methodology description

- *Describe methodology and all relevant steps undertaken (including approach to translation (if applicable), piloting and pre-testing steps)*

- Describe the set-up and content of the total survey (include descriptions of all included measures and items (e.g., psychosocial constructs, demographics etc.)) and the (experimental) design of the preference elicitation method.
- Describe how information on the decision context, exercise and attributes and levels was presented to respondents (e.g. educational tools or other educational material, if educational tools were developed please described the developmental process, pilot test stages etc. and place the tool (or screenshots) in the appendix).
- Any changes to the planned approach that might not have warranted separate ethics committee approvals
- Whenever available use evidence-based guidelines for the description of the methodology.
- Include total survey (see appendix)

2.2.4 Statistical considerations and data analysis

- Sample size calculation
- Planned respondents to be included in the analysis (completes versus all respondents)
- Planned analysis of patient disposition, demographics and other baseline characteristics
- Describe the following elements for each endpoint for each of the clinical RQ in a different section
 - Define the primary variable(s), i.e. the variable corresponding to the primary objective of the study
 - Describe the statistical hypothesis, model, and method of analysis
 - (if applicable) Anticipated sub-group analysis
 - Approach to handling missing values
 - Approach for assessing and analysing quality of the responses
 - (if applicable) Description of formal internal validity tests
- Describe the following elements for each endpoint for each of the methodological RQ in a different section
 - Define the primary variable(s), i.e. the variable corresponding to the primary objective of the study
 - Describe the statistical hypothesis, model, and method of analysis
 - Anticipated sub-group analysis
 - Approach to handling missing values
 - Approach for assessing and analysing quality of the responses
 - (if applicable) Description of formal internal validity tests
- Any changes to the planned approach

2.3 Involvement of patients in the entire case study

Describe the role of patient/representatives/caregivers throughout the conduct of the study. Clearly report how patient/representatives/caregivers have contributed to the design and conduct of the study and if/how the case study team made changes to their case study due to patient input. Make a distinction between the qualitative and quantitative study phases.

2.4 Involvement of other stakeholders in the entire case study

Describe the role of stakeholders (HTA, regulators, and industry) throughout the conduct of the study. Clearly report how stakeholders have contributed to the design and conduct of the study and if/how the case study team made changes to their case study due to stakeholder input.

2.5 Data Management

- *Data collection, data set description, handling and data sharing [please refer to the PREFER data management plan (especially section 5):
<https://service.projectplace.com/pp/pp.cgi/r1282329114>*
- *Please ensure that:*
 - *Details about which personal and/or sensitive data will be collected are described and submitted to IMI before the collection of data*
 - *Copies of approvals for the collection of personal data by the Institutional Data Protection Officer / National Data Protection authority are submitted to IMI before the collection of data*
 - *PREFER obtains written approval for the technical procedures that will be used for data protection for the project from each institution where data will be collected. These procedures must demonstrate compliance of the data protection processes with the present European legal frame. A copy of this approval will be submitted to IMI before the collection of data.*
 - *Detail of the level of de-identification of the different source of data and how protection of personal data is assured and approved by an ethical board and provided to IMI before the use of data*
 - *If personal and sensitive data will be processed and transferred between non-EU and EU countries, relevant authorizations are provided to IMI before the use of any personal/sensitive data not publicly available*
 - *Detailed information on dissemination of results in case of rare diseases is approved by the Ethical Committee and a copy of this approval is submitted to IMI before dissemination*
 - *Details of any planned exchanged or transfer of samples and personal data with non-EU countries together with appropriate authorizations are provided before transfer / exchange*

3. Results

3.1 Qualitative phase

3.1.1 Study subjects

Disposition of subjects (include description or chart running from: eligible for inclusion to completed survey and included analysed. Explain number of enrolled respondents and drop-out, response rate, etc.)

Demographic and other baseline characteristics

3.1.2 Results relating to the clinical RQ of the study

(please describe separate per RQ, include coding tree etc. (See appendix))

3.1.3 Results related to the methods RQ of this study

(please describe separate per RQ include coding tree etc. (see appendix))

3.2 Quantitative phase

3.2.1 Study subjects

Disposition of subjects (include description or chart running from: eligible for inclusion to completed survey and included analysed. Explain number of enrolled respondents and drop-out, response rate, etc.)

Demographic and other baseline characteristics

3.2.2 Results relating to the clinical RQ of the study

(please describe separate per RQ, report on all endpoints mentioned in the SAP, in concordance with evidence-based guidelines (if available), include appropriate tables and figures))

3.2.3 Results related to the methods RQ of this study

(please describe separate per RQ, report on all endpoints mentioned in the SAP, in concordance with evidence-based guidelines (if available), include appropriate tables and figures))

If multiple methods have been included in the case study, please clearly report:

- *Differences between the endpoints reported for the methods*
- *Differences in information retrieved from both methods*
- *Differences in usability and value of results of both methods to stakeholder decision making*
 - *Use the T2.3 report that lists the information needs of stakeholders per decision point as well as the decision criteria*
 - *Validate/confirm with stakeholder (group)*

4. Discussion

4.1 Summary of results and comparison to previous studies related to the clinical RQ

(please describe per RQ)

4.2 Summary of results and comparison to previous studies related to the methodological RQ

(please describe per RQ)

4.3 Contribution to decision making in the medical product life cycle

Describe how and to what extent the case study may be helpful for decision making along the MPLC

4.4 What was the impact of including patients in the case study

- *Describe how patient/representatives/caregivers involvement in the study influenced the approach of the study*
- *Describe how and when results are communicated back to patient/representatives/caregivers*

4.5 What was the impact of including other stakeholders in the case study

- *Describe how stakeholders (HTA, regulators, industry) involvement in the study influenced the approach of the study*
- *Describe how results are communicated back to stakeholders*

4.6 Study implications

Describe the implications of the study separately for:

- *Patients and/or caregivers*
- *Other stakeholders (industry, regulator HTA/payers)*
- *Academic research (future studies)*

4.7 Transferability of study results to other decision context

(Please describe an analysis of the transferability of study results to other decision contexts: other countries, other diseases within the same disease spectrum, other indications for same drug product and use transferability checklist of Task 3.10 for your analysis.

4.7 Study limitations

For each limitation indicate the impact on the study outcomes and specify potential mitigation strategies future studies might use.

4.7.1 Impact of COVID-19 on the case study conduct and report

- 5. Conclusion**
- 6. Repository for primary data**
- 7. References**
- 8. Tables**
- 9. Figures**

Appendix 1. Interview guide

Appendix 2. Coding tree used for the analysis of the Qualitative phase

Appendix 3. Survey

Please include the full survey. Regarding the choice tasks: depending on the method; include all choice task elements (for SW, Q), only the base case (for PTT) or example task (DCE, BWS) and specify the experimental design (for DCE and BWS studies include the experimental design in design coding, not the choice tasks themselves).

Appendix 4. Patient invitations and information sheets

For both the qualitative phase and quantitative phase

Appendix 3: Case study portfolio